

TRUSTWORTHINESS IN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION AND
INFORMATION LITERACY COMPETENCES IN EUROPEAN DOCTORAL
STUDENTS

A study submitted in partial fulfilment
of the requirements for the degree of
Master of Art in Library and Information Services Management

at

THE UNIVERSITY OF SHEFFIELD

by

FEDERICA SIGNORIELLO
180140987

Word-length: 14,526

August 2021

Abstract

Background. The issue of trust in scholarly communication has gained relevance in the literature without any specific focus on doctoral students. Moreover, the influence of the training received at master's level and the role of information literacy in the academic development of doctoral students were only addressed on a speculative level.

Aims. First, this study focused on the topic of trustworthiness in European doctoral students applied to the context of scholarly communication to ascertain the differences between this group and that of the “younger researchers” (under 30 years of age) who had been surveyed in 2013. Secondly, it aimed to explore the connection between the European doctoral students' trust in scholarly communication and their acquisition of information literacy during their previous degrees.

Methods. A mixed method was employed. In Phase A, a web survey provided quantitative data and the results were subsequently compared to the findings of a similar survey conducted on “younger researchers” in 2013. In Phase B, semi-structured interviews provided qualitative data, then analysed through grounded theory, which resulted in a theoretical model describing the process of acquisition of information literacy.

Results. Current European doctoral students do not differ greatly from “younger researchers” of 2013. They trust Open Access and distrust bibliometrics, however prioritising highly cited publishing outlets, mainly traditional scholarly publishers. They disregard web tools of dissemination. Their insecurities and lack of knowledge of scholarly communication derive from the passive or prescriptive approach to information literacy held by their previous universities and supervisors. When students are exposed early on to good publishing practices, they tend to be committed to them in the long term. Those who studied in several countries before their PhD held a better knowledge of scholarly communication and of academic publishing than their one-country counterparts.

Conclusions. The information literacy training given to master's degree students has a considerable impact on their trust of scholarly communication. Further research should focus more on them, on the state of information literacy in Europe and on the effects of European mobility (including Brexit) on doctoral programmes.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Prof. Peter Willett for the meticulous care that he put into the supervision of this dissertation and for his encouragement. Thanks also to all those EUI students interviewed for this research, as I was overwhelmed by their kindness and warmth, and those members of the EUI staff who sent the email invitation to fill in the web survey.

I am also lucky to have met many wonderful colleagues in various libraries where I worked throughout the past twelve years, including the University of Milan (Biblioteca di scienze dell'antichità e filologia moderna), London Business School and the Warburg Institute. Thanks to all of you. A special mention goes to those who taught me the secrets of metadata and supported me when I decided to apply for this degree – David Lowe and Sonia Morcillo García at Cambridge University Library, Iris O'Brien at the British Library – and to all staff at the EUI Library, especially Carlotta Alpigiano and Paolo Baglioni, with whom I discussed at length my ideas for the assignments and for this dissertation.

My warmest thank you goes to Patrizio for listening, reading, advising, waiting for me during all the long evenings of study and especially for the daily laughter shared throughout this journey.

Table of contents

Abstract	1
Acknowledgements	2
Table of contents	3
List of tables	5
List of figures	5
1 Introduction	6
1.1 Context and rationale	6
1.2 Aims and objectives	7
2 Literature review	9
2.1 Trustworthiness.....	9
2.2 Publishing during a doctorate.....	10
2.3 Competences in information literacy of doctoral students.....	11
2.4 Conclusions	13
3 Methodology	15
3.1 Phase A: Comparative analysis.....	15
3.1.1 Research strategy and design.....	15
3.1.2 Data collection: web survey.....	16
3.1.3 Sampling.....	17
3.1.4 Survey questions	18
3.1.5 Alterations.....	18
3.1.6 Increasing survey participation	19
3.1.7 Pilot study	21
3.1.8 Data analysis	21
3.2 Phase B: Exploratory research.....	22
3.2.1 Research strategy and design.....	22
3.2.2 Data collection: semi-structured interviews	22
3.2.3 Sampling.....	23
3.2.4 Interview questions	23
3.2.5 Grounded theory coding	23
3.3 Ethics.....	24
3.3.1 Ethics assessment and approval.....	24
3.3.2 Informed consent.....	24
3.3.3 Confidentiality	24
3.3.4 Data management	25
3.3.5 Risk assessment.....	25
4 Phase A: Results and discussion	26
4.1 Results of Phase A.....	26
4.1.1 Demographics.....	26
4.1.2 Usage and reading behaviour	28
4.1.3 Dissemination and publishing.....	31
4.1.4 Citing.....	35
4.2 Discussion of Phase A	37
4.2.1 Trustworthiness in European doctoral students	37
4.2.2 Comparison with Nicholas	38
5 Phase B: Results and discussion	41

5.1 Results of Phase B.....	41
5.1.1 Interviews.....	41
5.1.2 Causal conditions	42
5.1.3 Phenomenon resulting from causal conditions.....	45
5.1.4 Context in which the phenomenon developed and intervening conditions	46
5.1.5 Strategies for managing phenomenon	48
5.1.6 Consequences.....	49
5.2 Discussion of Phase B	51
6 Conclusions and recommendations.....	54
6.1 Summary of findings	54
6.2 Limitations.....	56
6.3 Recommendations for future research	57
7 Bibliography	58
8 Appendices	69
Appendix 1 – Web survey settings	69
Appendix 2 – Information provided to the web survey participants	70
Appendix 3 – Additional information given to the web survey participants	72
Appendix 4 – Web survey questions	75
Appendix 5 – Interview questions.....	79
Appendix 6 – Grounded theory coding	80
Appendix 7 – Research Ethics application form	83
Appendix 8 – Ethics certificate of approval.....	88
Appendix 9 – Data Management Plan.....	89
Appendix 10 – Risk assessment	91

List of tables

Table 1. Department breakdown	26
Table 2. Year breakdown	26
Table 3. Age breakdown	27
Table 4. Country of study	27
Table 5. Countries of study of the participants labelled "multinational"	28
Table 6. Question 1: How important do you consider each of these activities when deciding what information to use/read in your own research area?.....	29
Table 7. Question 2: To what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements?	31
Table 8. Question 3: As an author, how important are the following attributes of an outlet when deciding where to disseminate/publish your research work?	32
Table 9. Question 4: To what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements concerning the quality and trustworthiness of places to publish/disseminate your research?	33
Table 10. Question 5: How characteristic of your discipline are each of the citing practices listed below?	35
Table 11. Question 6: To what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements concerning the quality and trustworthiness of the sources you cite? .	36

List of figures

Figure 1. Theoretical model for the acquisitions of knowledge of scholarly communication and academic publishing	42
Figure 2. Graphic representation of the causal conditions determining particular phenomena associated to information literacy functional to scholarly communication	43

1 Introduction

1.1 Context and rationale

Ever since the Bologna Process was initiated by the signing of the Bologna Declaration of 1999, the EU member states, followed by other non-EU countries, have committed to harmonise and develop a coherent system of higher education across borders in order to boost its quality and enhance the mobility of students and researchers.

Among the numerous changes that occurred in the last two decades, those that concern academic research are complex to investigate and analyse, and more so when we consider the doctoral phase. The Bologna process did not directly reshape the so-called “third cycle” of study, i.e. doctorates, as tightly as it did with undergraduate and taught postgraduate studies. Practical guidelines for their coordination were given only in 2010 with the Salzburg II Recommendations, issued by the European University Association (2010). Five years later, a new set of recommendations took into account the relevance of digitalisation and of the globalisation of research (European University Association, 2016). As these, nonetheless, are only suggestions, “doctoral programmes are still plagued by structural, organisational, and conceptual vagueness” (Prøitz & Wittek, 2020).

In addition to institutional changes, doctorates around the world have been affected by the radical transformations in scholarly communication brought by the digital transition, which altered the way all researchers deal with information seeking, reading, citing and with the dissemination of research (Ince et al., 2019). In addition to this, another factor that has rapidly changed the approach to scholarly communication is the increasing pressure to publish during the doctoral studies, to the extent that some academic institutions accept a number of articles published in scholarly journals in lieu of a dissertation (European University Association, 2005). There are many factors to be accounted for this phenomenon, such as the competitive job market in academia and the fluctuating distribution of funding to universities and research projects (Horta & Santos, 2016). What is certain is that, in addition to their standard workload, doctoral students are also increasingly driven to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary to publish much earlier than what was customary only a few years ago (Jalongo et al., 2014).

1.2 Aims and objectives

Given the complexities that doctoral students are currently experiencing, this dissertation aims at exploring the link between the issue of trustworthiness in scholarly communication and academic publishing and information literacy in the context of European academia.

The specific objectives are the following:

- a) Examine the existing literature about these topics: trustworthiness in reading, citing and publishing; the issue of publishing during the doctoral programme; the competences in information literacy of doctoral students.
- b) Investigate the topic of trustworthiness in doctoral students applied to the context of scholarly communication. This topic is pivotal in the academic context, as “trustworthiness, authority and quality [...] are the very watchwords of scholarly communication, a system designed to deliver quality assurance” (Nicholas et al., 2015). As today’s scholarly communication is mostly digital, its growth is constant and haphazard. Thus, recognising and trusting a journal, a platform or a publisher is not always a straight-forward process.
- c) Compare findings of (b) with those of Nicholas et al. (2015) to ascertain (i) the differences between those who in 2013 would have been called “younger researchers” and current doctoral students (ii) whether the different geographical focus plays any role, that is, if the countries where these students were trained before starting their PhD affected them.
- d) Investigate the correlation between the assessment of trustworthiness in doctoral students and their competences in information literacy.

When students transition from a taught postgraduate course to a doctorate, not only do they carry with them the wealth of knowledge acquired through past courses, but they also transfer from programme to programme a set of skills. Initially, these should allow them to efficiently perform information seeking, reading and citing. Their competence in information literacy, in fact, hardly encompasses “the increasingly complex ecosystem of publications, platforms, and tools that scholars, scientists, and researchers use to share their work with each other and with other interested readers”, that is,

knowledge of scholarly communication (Ince et al., 2019; Anderson, 2018). Postgraduate students, therefore, may reach the doctoral programmes with none or little mastery of academic writing for publication and awareness of concepts like peer review, bibliometrics, Open Access and the differences between academic journals and publishers in the same field. This, however, might not be true in the same extent for all doctoral candidates in Europe, as the approach to information literacy varies significantly across European countries (Basili, 2011). This second phase of the research, therefore, does not pay so much attention to the country of provenance of doctoral researchers as at the countries where they received their undergraduate and postgraduate education, taking into account the mobility programmes promoted by European integration and the Bologna Process.

- e) Make recommendations for future research.

2 Literature review

2.1 Trustworthiness

The earliest publication about trust in scholarly communication and the digital transition is that of Speier et al. (1999) who explored prestige and legitimacy of electronic journals in relation to faculty members. Since then, with the growth of digital publications, the focus of research changed from the novelty of digital journals to the process with which researchers, especially “younger researchers” lacking publishing experience, deal when they decide where to submit for publication. Some scholars adopted a theoretical approach and proposed the establishment of methods for benchmarking scientific journals, like Björk & Holmström (2006), or argued against the practice of evaluating journals based solely on a quantitative measure such as the Impact Factor, like West and Rich (2012). Others attempted to investigate academics by way of surveys, and by comparing individual perceptions of prestige with the actual impact factor of certain journals, for example Catling et al. (2009) in the field of psychology and Manzari (2013) and Taylor and Willett (2017) in the field of Library and Information Science.

A comprehensive investigation into trustworthiness in reading, citing and publishing was undertaken by the research project “Trust and authority in scholarly communication in the light of the digital transition” founded by the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation in 2012–2013. This resulted in three distinct publications documenting the various phases of the research, hence focusing on refining the research questions (Nicholas et al., 2014), on the geographical differences of the results obtained (Jamali et al., 2014) and on “younger researchers” (Nicholas et al., 2015). The project finally surveyed 3,650 authors from around the world in all disciplines, who had published articles in international journals. The findings showed how researchers developed methods of establishing trust and how suspicious they were about Open Access; how citation derived metrics were becoming part of the criteria to choose where to publish and that social media were used for self-promotion. Further analysis determined that there are significant differences between researchers from countries with medium or very high Human Development Index and that “younger researchers”, that is, researchers who were thirty and under thirty years old in 2013, distinguished themselves in some respects. On the one hand, “younger researchers” tended to privilege ease of access to information and they

were also likely to compromise on quality, but on the other hand they were less sceptical than their senior colleagues about Open Access and social media.

After this study, Nicholas et al. focussed further on early career researchers, i.e. those with less than ten years of career since the completion of their PhD (2020). This qualitative research, aimed at determining whether the newest generation of researchers were really the “harbingers of change”, involved subjects from all over the world working in all disciplines and confirmed the universal popularity of Google Scholar and ResearchGate, the fact that researchers are aware of the benefits of Open Access and finally that social media are used as source of discovering scholarly information.

Finally, in a recent investigation by Owens and Manolovitz (2021) conducted among faculty members and graduate students from all disciplines at Sam Houston State University, the trustworthiness towards certain aspects of scholarly communication was tested. The respondents were still doubtful about newer models for Open Access publishing such as the article processing charges (APCs), and also about open data, whereas graduate students expressed interest in face-to-face professional development sessions in all areas of scholarly communication.

2.2 Publishing during a doctorate

Nowadays doctoral candidates find themselves facing the world of scholarly communication primarily during the process of seeking and assessing information. Later on, this becomes a decisive problem whenever they disseminate their work and decide to publish a piece of original research. Remarkably, all the literature cited below describes the process of writing for publication and the dissemination of research as “implicit knowledge” and discusses the “unwritten” conventions of different disciplines.

Kwan was the first to address this matter (2010) in the context of Asian universities with a study that suggests the implementation of an Instruction in Research Publication for doctoral programmes to strategically prepare the future faculty for the early phase of their career. Likewise, the qualitative approach of Jalongo et al. (2014), later corroborated by the work of Badenhorst and Xu (2016), highlights how doctoral students in the USA, Canada and Australia lack knowledge on how to write for professional publication. Moreover, they argue that it would be beneficial to begin instruction in scholarly publishing even before the doctorate and to maintain it

across all stages of the programme. Conversely, the faculty members in the fields of business and management surveyed by Wilkins et al. (2021), deem the introduction of doctoral students to academic publishing a responsibility of their supervisors.

Research on this topic that involved European doctoral students is limited to the study of Nagano and Spiczéné Bukovszki (2016). Through a survey conducted among Hungarian doctoral students, they concluded that among them there are considerable differences between students in Humanities and Social Sciences as opposed to students in Engineering.

2.3 Competences in information literacy of doctoral students

Over the last fifteen years, the assessment of information literacy competencies in doctoral students has enjoyed some attention, perhaps prompted by the dramatic increase of digital information resources.

Much of the literature about this topic was born out of the need of academic librarians to understand and cope with the needs of their users. Various papers, therefore, describe research projects aimed at assessing the competence in information literacy of doctoral students. The study conducted at Carnegie Mellon University by George et al. (2006), for example, was the first to exclusively involve graduate students. It revealed how convenience, lack of sophistication in finding and using resources and course requirements affected their information behaviour, in which web resources already played a major role. Vezzosi (2009) followed with her investigation of the information behaviour of a group of doctoral students in the field of biology at the University of Parma (Italy), which disclosed how students heavily relied on both the Internet and on other people's suggestions of relevant documents. Wiorogórska (2014), unlike the other authors, framed her research into the implementation of Bologna Process and the adoption of qualification frameworks for the EHEA. Her comparative research looked at the doctoral students at the University of Warsaw and the University of Lille, revealing that in Poland there was a lack of training addressed to doctoral students, while in France there was no promotion of such instruction among doctoral students and lecturers.

Delaney & Bates (2018) performed a comprehensive description of doctoral students' information behaviour at Ulster University based on qualitative analysis. This article is particularly noteworthy as the authors emphasise that a relevant

percentage of doctoral students at Ulster University is international, hence the information needs to be considered are very diverse. Among their findings, they establish that students made minimal use of social media or apps and that, despite their expression of confidence in their own abilities, the students were not as able to correctly identify different source types within a reference.

In 2019 Moore & Singley focused on US doctoral students in the humanities at Boston College and at the University of Notre Dame. Through the analysis of a series of interviews, they concluded that the supervisor-supervisee relationship should be investigated further as a pivotal vehicle of information literacy. This kind of study was later carried out by Nylander & Hjort (2020) who researched the information literacy habits of PhD students at the Research School of Health and Welfare in Jönköping (Sweden) and those of their supervisors. While both supervisors and supervisees are often unaware of the services provided by their library, supervisors have a tendency to assume that their doctoral students already have the skills needed to complete their course, when often this is not true.

Today information literacy programmes targeted specifically at doctoral students are common to find in academia, and the evaluation of their impact is the subject of in-depth analysis. For example, the impact of a mandatory training in information literacy for doctoral students in Civil and Geodetic Engineering at the University of Ljubljana (introduced in the Bologna reformed PhD study programme since 2009) was researched by Koler-Povh & Turk (2020). Its effect was measured by the number of cited references in the PhD theses, which increased in the post-Bologna reform students. Notably, part of the new doctoral programme requires also the publication of an article in a JCR-ranked journal, an obligation that is also directly correlated to the improvement in managing references.

Other studies in this field focused on specific types of doctoral population, such as that of Chinese PhD students in Australia (Han, 2012). This research revealed significant information literacy challenges due to the unfamiliarity with terminology, learning environment, academic culture, and in general with an alien political and cultural system of values. The adaptation to these values affected the proficiency in information technology and in accessing, processing and controlling information of the Chinese doctoral students. By contrast, when cultural differences are negligible to foreign students, other factors may come into play, as revealed by Oyewo &

Umoh Uwem (2016). Their qualitative study comparing the experience of Nigerian PhD students at the University of Lagos, Nigeria and at the University of Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa, shows meaningful differences between the two institutions. The quality of the information literacy training and of the resources provided to them affects their evaluation of literature materials, their publishing, their access to conferences and grant applications.

Other contributions on this topic are of a speculative nature. The launch in 2010 of the online portal Form@doct (Serres, n.d.) managed by the Université Bretagne Loire, which aims at providing doctoral students with specialised tutorials, produced a series of considerations and methodological papers dealing with information literacy and distance learning. Among them, Malingre and Serres (2011) reflected on the relationship between the contents of the information literacy training aimed at doctoral students and the knowledge and skills already acquired through a master's degree, concluding that it is difficult for those in charge of teaching information literacy at this level to find a balance between novelty and going in depth in their instruction. They maintain that it is nearly impossible to establish a framework of progressive competence in information literacy because doctoral candidates are characterised by a great diversity that depends on their previous education, on their cultural background and on their country of provenance.

Another perspective is explored by Tara Brabazon, Dean of Graduate Research at Flinders University and Nazlin Bhimani, UCL Institute of Education Library. In their recording (*Vlog 32 Information Literacy for PhD Students*, 2016) the expression "digital literacy" frequently substitutes that of "information literacy" and, unlike Malingre & Serres (2011), Brabazon and Bhimani reflect on the role of information literacy in the development and professional future of the doctoral students, rather than on the relevance of past training received in their master's degree. Additionally, they argue that information literacy should be embedded in their practice, research and teaching, and that it enables the students to develop professional working practices, which help establish themselves as experts in their field.

2.4 Conclusions

The issue of trust in scholarly communication has gained relevance in the last twenty years with the digital transition and with the growth of electronic publications. The process with which academics deal when they decide where to submit for

publication and other matters germane to this issue were investigated by focusing on geographical variances and on “younger” and expert researchers. Disciplinary differentiations, however, were not thoroughly investigated and neither were doctoral students as population. The latter, nevertheless, are increasingly struggling with scholarly communication as their need to publish presses them during their doctoral programmes. This process to them is far from transparent and it requires implicit knowledge brought by the unwritten conventions of the different disciplines.

The level of information literacy in doctoral students and its dynamics were investigated. Among the dynamics studied in this context, there are the processes of information seeking and retrieving, the quality of the training provided during the doctoral programme, the value of the information exchanged with peers and with supervisors and the difficulties encountered by foreign PhD students. The influence of the training received during their master’s degree and the role of information literacy in the future professional life of PhD students were only addressed on a speculative level.

This research seeks to address the gaps in the literature by assessing the trust in scholarly communication of doctoral candidates in the social sciences and humanities (objective (b)). The results, compared to those obtained by Nicholas (2015), will highlight whether there are any differences between “younger researchers” and doctoral students (objective (c)). Moreover, the second part of this research will explore the connection between the students’ trust in scholarly communication and their information literacy, more specifically the training received before beginning a PhD, and will look into geographical and disciplinary differences (objective (d)).

3 Methodology

This research project, aiming to address the aforementioned gap in the literature, comprises the following phases:

- A.** To achieve objectives (b) and (c): investigating the topic of trustworthiness in doctoral students applied to the context of scholarly communication by replicating Nicholas' (2015) study among doctoral students at the European University Institute (henceforth EUI) and comparing findings with those of Nicholas to determine the degree of correlation between doctoral students and “younger researchers”.
- B.** To achieve objective (d): exploring the correlation between trustworthiness in scholarly communication in doctoral students and the acquisition of their competences in information literacy.

3.1 Phase A: Comparative analysis

3.1.1 Research strategy and design

During phase A, comparative research was employed to identify “similarities and differences between social entities” (Lewis-Beck et al., 2004) and in this case specifically, between 1) academic researchers who in 2013 were under thirty years of age and had published at least one article in a traditional scholarly journal, working anywhere in the world and in any discipline; and 2) doctoral candidates in 2021 of any age in the following disciplines: Economics, History, Law and Political Science. These students are from the twenty-three contracting states of the EUI at the time of this research (European University Institute, 2020): Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, plus the United Kingdom, which was a contracting state until 31 January 2021 (*The European University Institute (EU Exit) Regulations 2019*, 2019; *Explanatory Memorandum to the European University Institute (EU Exit) Regulations 2019*, 2019).

Data on European doctoral students were collected and analysed with empirical research, while Nicholas' study about “younger researchers” was employed as a comparator.

In comparative research, the selection of the entities to compare is a crucial issue affecting the analysis of variations across different categories – for instance, Nicholas’ group of “younger researchers” of the study carried out in 2015 was a subset of a larger group of 3,650 academic researchers (Jamali et al., 2014). The arbitrary choice of selecting among those the researchers under thirty years old generated a “constructed population”, i.e., a theory driven category and therefore subject to bias. On the other hand, the category “doctoral researchers” responds to the definition of “given population”, which could also lead to partialities as it may not be as homogeneous and predictable as the given parameters lead to believe (Ragin, 2006). Moreover, other factors should be taken into account in the comparison between the groups chosen in this research:

- Nicholas’ researchers were surveyed in 2013, and this research took place 8 years later. In this period of time scholarly communication have evolved and so did the habits of scholars in this context.
- The countries of origin of Nicholas’ researchers were distributed among all continents, whereas the group chosen for comparison was made out of European doctoral students.
- Nicholas’ researchers were selected on the basis of their age and held a variety of roles, including students (unspecified), part-time and full-time researchers and faculty members, while the group chosen for comparison comprised only doctoral students, regardless of their age.
- Nicholas’ group of “younger researchers” counted 368 individuals who responded to the web survey, which was organised on a global scale with the assistance of major publishing houses advertising to their authors. The lack of time to carry out a systematic pursue of survey respondents for this study resulted in a smaller group of doctoral students.

3.1.2 Data collection: web survey

Participants were asked a set of six questions about information practices, reading habits and information, dissemination, and citation practices plus personal demographics via web survey. In Nicholas’ original study, data collection was performed in the same way, as web surveys are an efficient and cost-effective mode to reach a wide number of subjects and store the subsequent data. Notwithstanding

the tendency of a low response rate for web surveys (Hughes, 2012), they excel in providing the safest solution to submit a questionnaire during the COVID-19 pandemic, which was still imposing strict limits to otherwise normal face-to-face interactions during the time period covered by data collection (Tobin et al., 2020; Howlett, 2021).

The questionnaire was created with the web-based survey administration software Google Forms. Google Forms, part of the Google suite provided by the University of Sheffield, was chosen against other free web-based software because of its safe data storage, anonymisation of the responses, export and aggregation of results, ease of use. After authorisation was sought from the EUI's Academic Service, an email was sent to all four departmental coordinators explaining the project. Subsequently, the link to the web survey was emailed to the participants by the departmental coordinators, along with links to further information about the study.

The specific settings applied to the web survey are listed in Appendix 1, while Appendix 2 and 3 contain the information provided to the participants.

3.1.3 Sampling

To this day, the Bologna Process has been adopted by forty-nine countries forming the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), whose main goal is to “increase staff and students’ mobility and facilitate employability” (*European Higher Education Area and Bologna Process*, 2021). Membership to the EHEA is not limited to EU member countries, as the Bologna Process employs a broader definition of “Europe” developed by the Council of Europe (Voegtler, 2014, p. 11). Ideally, the present research would encompass doctoral researchers from the whole EHEA, as the shared policies of these countries, considered altogether as a theoretically significant factor, reduce variances and allow them to be categorised as a sub-group of the global community of researchers (Øyen, 1990, p. 43).

Time and financial limitations, however, constrained the data that I was able to collect and led me to choose a further subgroup of the EHEA doctoral students, i.e. the students at the EUI, where I am employed as librarian. The countries of provenance of the current doctoral candidates at the EUI are twenty-four, as explained at paragraph 3.1.1, i.e. about half of the countries belonging to the EHEA. Conversely, all contracting states of the EUI (including the UK until 31 January 2021), being members of the EU as per the EUI's convention (European University

Institute, 2020), constitute a more homogeneous group than the whole EHEA in terms of access to education and shared interests. The EU member states constitute, as a matter of fact, a further coalition named the European Education Area (EEA, *European Education Area*, 2018). The EU and EEA member states not participating in the EUI project are Croatia, Czechia, Hungary and Lithuania.

In addition to geographical limitations, a further characterisation of this sample is given by the disciplines studied at the EUI, that are economics, history, law and political and social sciences. The disciplines excluded from this sample are broadly those embraced by the acronym STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics).

Finally, a total of 628 doctoral students were invited to fill in the questionnaire, whereas Nicholas' study had an unknown number of potential respondents and 368 completed the survey.

3.1.4 Survey questions

The original questionnaire, which is employed in this research with a few alterations, was developed with focus groups and one-to-one interviews (the process is described in Nicholas et al., 2014 and Jamali et al., 2014) resulting "a little unusual in featuring statements made by focus groups participants" (Nicholas et al., 2015). This questionnaire included twelve questions about decision making in the contexts of scholarly reading, citing, and publishing, for a total of ninety-six statements to be evaluated on Likert scales ranking their importance or agreement, plus a section with eleven demographics questions (about subject area, institution of affiliation, type of employment, whether the participant had ever been a journal editor or reviewer, years of experience, number of articles published, country of work, age, gender), and a final section for further comments (Tenopir et al., 2016).

3.1.5 Alterations

The length of a web survey can dramatically affect both the response rate and data quality, especially if it exceeds twenty minutes (Hugick & Best, 2011). Provided that the original questionnaire was lengthy and, when tested, its completion took more than twenty minutes, the number of questions and statements was reduced following three criteria.

First, notions that are not relatable to doctoral students were disregarded. This resulted in the exclusion of question 5: “Effect on policies where you publish: do research policy directives/mandates (e.g. national, university, departmental) influence where you publish your research?”; of the subsequent question 6: “You said yes to the previous question, how are you influenced?”; and finally of question 12: “To what extent do these statements represent what has happened in your research field over the past decade or so?”.

Secondly, in view of comparing the results of this survey to those pertaining the “younger scholars” as in the analysis provided by Nicholas, some statements from the original survey were not included. As Nicholas’ analysis was itself a comparative study between older and younger researchers, the statements that did not show statistically significant differences in the responses of these two populations were excluded. The statements withdrawn following these two criteria are fifty-six, bringing the total number of statements from ninety-six to forty-four.

Finally, demographics questions were reduced to five, i.e. those necessary for the purposes of this research: department of affiliation (that is, discipline), year into the doctoral programme, age range, country or countries where the respondents studied before starting their doctorate, and email address in case they gave their consent to be interviewed.

In addition to these changes, and in order to gather ancillary qualitative data to inform Phase B of this research, participants were given the opportunity to leave a free text comment after every question about trustworthiness and after the demographic questions.

The questions may be found in Appendix 4.

3.1.6 Increasing survey participation

A description of this project and the receipt of the ethics approval from the University of Sheffield was sent to the EUI’s central academic administration to seek permission to send the web survey to the EUI doctoral students. Their approval was met, on the condition that the link to the web survey would be sent by email by the departmental administrators with a view to 1. increase the credibility of this research and 2. distinguish between my professional role as outreach librarian at the EUI and my affiliation to the University of Sheffield as master’s degree student. These

emails, sent between 2 February and 12 February 2021, resulted in fifty-seven completed questionnaires.

This procedure did not allow me to send direct reminder and follow-up mailings, even though this is the most effective technique to produce high response rates (Dialsingh, 2011). In order to compensate for this lack of email reminders, about ten days after the web survey was sent by email, I posted a reminder in a closed group on the social media platform Facebook (*EUI Community - Formerly EUI newcomers 2.0*, 2021). This online platform allows the creation of closed groups in which members are accepted only by some designed administrators. In September 2016, some EUI students created the closed group “EUI newcomers 2.0”, later renamed “EUI Community - Formerly EUI newcomers 2.0” in which any person affiliated to the EUI can join and informally share any kind of information. After posting my survey reminder on 19 February 2021, twenty more people filled the questionnaire bringing the total of responses to seventy-seven.

Efforts to increase survey participation were otherwise made by adopting measures to decrease the “respondent fatigue” (Ben-Nun, 2011):

- Reducing the length of the questionnaire as described in paragraph 3.1.6. An estimate time of completion of the survey (12 minutes) was given in the emails sent to the students and in the web survey’s introductory paragraph.
- The web survey’s introductory paragraph, albeit giving enough information to the participants about the scope of this project, was brief and was complemented by hyperlinks to documents providing more detailed information (see Appendix 2).

Moreover, additional assurances were provided to the respondents:

- Emphasis was placed on confidentiality and data protection in the web survey’s introductory paragraph.
- My contact details (from my affiliation with the University of Sheffield) as well as those of my supervisor were given in the emails, in the web survey and in the documents linked to the web survey.

3.1.7 Pilot study

Even though the questions and statements of this web survey had already been piloted and used on a large scale, the usability of my web survey was tested by my supervisor and by two other acquaintances of mine unrelated to the EUI and both, as my supervisor, qualified with a doctoral degree and with experience in academic publishing. All the aforementioned people reported no anomalies nor difficulties in filling in the survey.

3.1.8 Data analysis

Aggregated survey results were downloaded from Google Forms and analysed with the spreadsheet software Microsoft Excel.

The survey respondents were supposed to rank their agreement or the importance of the statements on Likert scales. Replicating Nicholas' questionnaire, all Likert scales indicated with 5 the highest level of agreement or importance.

Likert scale data are inherently ordinal, however, for the purpose of comparing data to that provided by Nicholas, for each statement the following values were calculated:

- Mean value of importance or agreement;
- Standard deviation;
- A paired-sample t-test was performed and the p-value calculated against the null hypothesis that the difference between these groups' means, μ_1 and μ_2 , is equal to 0.

In addition to this analysis, further investigation was undertaken in preparation for Phase B of this research. The mean value of importance or agreement for each statement was examined in relation to some independent variables: department, year into the doctoral programme, age range, country where respondents were educated before the doctorate. As this analysis did not highlight any significant pattern, a further attempt was made to group the countries by significant categories in order to obtain another meaningful independent category. European Universities, however, present an exceptional diversity which only allows for a multi-dimensional mapping of European higher education and no well-defined classification can be

used for the purposes of this research (see the monograph by Niederl et al., 2014, pp. v-vii, which presents the results of a project led by the European Commission).

3.2 Phase B: Exploratory research

3.2.1 Research strategy and design

Phase B was mainly concerned with exploratory research as it investigated an overlooked aspect of academic research. This phase focused on the exploration of the information literacy taught to students before they started their doctoral programmes. It aimed, therefore, to develop a theory about the relationship between trustworthiness in scholarly communication in doctoral students and the information literacy competences acquired beforehand, hence following a grounded theory pattern (Glaser & Strauss, 1967).

3.2.2 Data collection: semi-structured interviews

Assuming that the landscape of information literacy teaching across the European universities is varied, the best way to elicit information from doctoral students about their past education is to conduct semi-structured interviews.

On the one hand, semi-structured interviews allow consistency through closed questions about the nature of the information literacy programmes followed by doctoral students in their past. On the other hand, open-ended questions encourage the students to reveal their own attitudes towards information literacy and scholarly communication (Moore, 2006, pp. 141-142).

The interviews were carried out on the online platform Zoom as they took place during the COVID-19 pandemic. Online interviewing presents many benefits such as logistical convenience and ease of recording. In addition to these advantages, the software of Zoom separates automatically the audio and video files, allowing the interview to take place with the camera switched on, while it is possible to reassure the interviewees that the data kept for research purposes concerns only the audio produced during the interview. Nevertheless, online interviewing presents some critical issues, for example limited interaction compared to face-to-face conversation and possible technical difficulties such as a faulty Internet connection (Dodds & Hess, 2020).

The audio files of the interviews were subsequently employed to produce “unfocused” or “broad” transcriptions, as at this stage there was no specific analytic focus (Gibson & Brown, 2009, p. 114).

3.2.3 Sampling

Interviewees were selected among those who participated in the web survey of Phase A and gave their consent to be interviewed.

Among these students, preference was given to those who studied in more than one country before their doctorate. In addition to this criterion, other interviewees were chosen with the objective of obtaining as a diverse sample as possible in regard to year into the doctoral programme, age range, country and department of affiliation.

3.2.4 Interview questions

The informants were asked a series of closed questions and open-ended questions (see Appendix 5), which were formulated after the collection and analysis of data in Phase A. The interviews explored mainly the education received by students before starting their doctoral programmes and in particular during their master’s degree, with a on finding and assessing academic material to read, citing and publishing. The final purpose of the interviews was to understand how the participants acquired these competences and how this process influenced their attitudes towards scholarly communication.

3.2.5 Grounded theory coding

The interview transcriptions were analysed and coded by following the procedures foreseen by grounded theory. This research method was chosen as it allows to go beyond description and it enables the generation of a theory and a general exploration of a process, grounded in the data provided by those who participated in the process itself (Creswell, 2007, pp. 62-63).

In grounded theory, coding can take different forms, which depend on the kind of approach adopted (Flick, 2018, pp. 49-66). The method used in this research was that of open coding, i.e., segmenting the interview transcripts in units and examining them for relevant categories of information.

A total of sixty-eight codes, therefore, were attached to segments of text that were deemed significant. In order to identify and classify the links between the codes, the axial coding paradigm by Strauss and Corbin (1990, p. 124) was employed. From this process, categories were developed, and finally selective coding was employed in order to put categories in relation to each other. When the exploration of codes and categories reached saturation, i.e. when the analysis of data did not generate any new codes or categories, all the data were incorporated in the core categories of the grounded theory paradigm (Strauss, 1987). See Appendix 6 for an overview of codes, categories and subcategories.

Finally, in the aforementioned Strauss and Corbin paradigm, two axes organise data by connecting categories and their subcategories. As one axis connects causes to a central phenomenon to its consequences, the second axis joins both context and the strategies adopted by those who participated in the phenomenon to the phenomenon themselves.

3.3 Ethics

3.3.1 Ethics assessment and approval

As the research proposal for this project was assessed as “low risk”, it was subsequently submitted to the ethics approval of the University of Sheffield (see the Research Ethics application form, Appendix 7) which was granted on 21/12/2020 (see the Ethics certificate of approval in Appendix 8).

3.3.2 Informed consent

Participants were informed on the scope and methods of this project on the first page of the web survey. A hyperlink was also provided to a public document in which the project was more thoroughly described along with reassurances on the fact that participation was voluntary, on confidentiality, data management, ethics clearance, and my contact details, those of my supervisor and of the Head of the Information School at the University of Sheffield (see Appendix 3).

The second page of the web survey constituted a consent form (see Appendix 2).

3.3.3 Confidentiality

In the said hyperlinked document, participants were assured that the information collected about them during the course of the research would be kept strictly

confidential and would only be accessible to me. To those who gave their consent to be interviewed it was specified that the audio recordings would be used only for analysis.

3.3.4 Data management

A research data management plan (see Appendix 9) was created to comply with the University of Sheffield's Research Data Management Policy (University of Sheffield, 2021).

3.3.5 Risk assessment

The risk assessment required by the University of Sheffield was undertaken and it is documented in Appendix 10.

4 Phase A: Results and discussion

4.1 Results of Phase A

4.1.1 Demographics

Seventy-seven out of 628 doctoral students (12.26%) completed the survey. This response is impossible to compare to that of Nicholas's study, as his number of potential respondents is unknown, while the total number of "younger researchers" is 368.

The disciplinary breakdown of the respondents is provided in Table 1. The proportion of subjects concerned with humanities ("History and Civilisation") is about a quarter of the total, while in Nicholas' group they are 5.43%, against 39.94% of scholars in the social sciences, 29.07% in the physical sciences, 23.09% in the life sciences and 2.47% unknown.

Table 1. Department breakdown

Department	n	%
Department of Economics	11	14.2%
Department of History and Civilisation	21	27.2%
Department of Law	25	32.4%
Department of Political and Social Sciences	20	25.9%
Total	77	100%

Nearly half of the respondents were in an advanced phase of their doctorate, while the rest comprised mainly students in the first or second year (Table 2), whereas Nicholas' group was composed of full-time researchers (31.8%), part-time researchers (12.2%), full-time faculty members (10.3%), part-time faculty members (3.3%), students (37.5%) and 4.6% of people in none of the previous categories.

Table 2. Year breakdown

Year into PhD	n	%
1st year	17	22%
2nd year	17	22%
3rd year	9	11.6%
4th+ year	34	44.1%
Total	77	100%

The age breakdown of the doctoral students is provided in Table 3. 71.43% of them was 30 years old or younger, as was 100% of Nicholas' sample.

Table 3. Age breakdown

Age range	N	%
20-25 years old	6	7.7%
25-30 years old	49	63.6%
30+ years old	22	28.5%
Total	77	100%

Finally, 100% of the respondents in this study were European, while Europeans were 9.9% of Nicholas' respondents. The remainder of Nicholas' sample was 16% from Africa, 25.6% from Asia, 6.5% from Australia and Oceania, 25.5% from the Middle East, 5.1% from North America, and 11% from South and Central America.

This web survey comprised an original demographic question that is essential to prepare Phase B of this research, i.e. the country or countries where the respondents studied before beginning their doctoral programme. The sample was quite diverse (Table 4), with twenty-three countries, including two extra-European countries such as Brazil and the United States, and seven respondents who studied in more than one country, labelled in Table 4 as "multinational".¹

Table 4. Country of study

Country of study	n	%
France	8	10.4%
Spain	7	9.1%
Multinational	7	9.1%
United Kingdom	7	9.1%
Portugal	6	7.8%
Italy	6	7.8%
Poland	5	6.5%
Finland	4	5.2%
Germany	4	5.2%
The Netherlands	3	3.9%

¹ The respondents who originally declared in their answer to have studied in more than one country were four. Three more were added after the interviews carried out in Phase B of this project revealed that they studied in more countries than previously stated in the web survey.

Sweden	2	2.6%
Belgium	2	2.6%
United States	2	2.6%
Switzerland	2	2.6%
Denmark	2	2.6%
Greece	2	2.6%
Ireland	1	1.3%
Romania	1	1.3%
Hungary	1	1.3%
Slovakia	1	1.3%
Brazil	1	1.3%
Norway	1	1.3%
Austria	1	1.3%
Luxembourg	1	1.3%
Grand Total	77	100%

The category “multinational”, is detailed in Table 5. The variety of countries is considerable, as is the presence of the United Kingdom in five out of seven “multinational” lists.

Table 5. Countries of study of the participants labelled "multinational"

Participant	Countries of study
Multinational 1	Belarus, Lithuania
Multinational 2	Italy, United Kingdom
Multinational 3	The Netherlands, United Kingdom
Multinational 4	Spain, Germany, Portugal, Belgium
Multinational 5	Spain, United Kingdom, Germany, Norway
Multinational 6	Ireland, United Kingdom, Spain
Multinational 7	France, United Kingdom

4.1.2 Usage and reading behaviour

Even though Nicholas deems that “this is the scholarly activity that is least prescribed for researchers as, in theory anyway, researchers can use/read what they want”, finding and selecting reading material for research are not skills to be taken for granted in postgraduate students. SCOUNL, for instance, lists them

among the abilities needed to be proficient in the evaluation of information (SCONUL Working Group on Information Literacy, 2011).

Question 1 (Table 6) asked to rate the importance of ten activities related to using and reading on a scale of not important (1), somewhat important (2), important (3), very important (4), extremely important (5).² Reading the abstract was the most important activity (question 1.1) for both European and “younger researchers”, although this was an activity of greater importance to European researchers. Unlike the “younger researchers”, the second most important activity that drives European researchers was checking whether the arguments and logic presented in the content are sound (question 1.3).

The ratings showing notable differences between the two groups are three. The activity of checking whether the source is indexed by an authoritative indexing body (1.5) and that of checking to see how many times it has been downloaded or accessed (1.9) were less important to European students than “younger researchers”, while the activity of checking the name of the publisher (1.8) was more important to European students than to “younger researchers”.

Table 6. Question 1: How important do you consider each of these activities when deciding what information to use/read in your own research area? (Mean rating, 1= not important to 5= extremely important)

	EU doctoral students			Nicholas’ “younger researchers”			d
	M	n	SD	M	n	SD	
1.1 Reading the abstract	4.48	77	0.75	4.21	366	1.01	0.27**
1.2 Checking to see whether the data used in the research are credible	3.99	77	1.06	4.18	365	0.09	0.19
1.3 Checking whether the arguments and logic presented in the content are sound	4.36	77	0.67	4.14	366	0.85	0.22***
1.4 Checking to see if it is peer reviewed	3.65	77	1.09	3.50	361	1.14	0.15

² The description of the scale at p. 51 of Nicholas’ article, which reverses the scale, is but a typo, as the correct order is given in the caption of Table 5.

1.5 Checking whether the source is indexed by an authoritative indexing body (e.g. LexisNexis, Web of Science, EconBiz, OpenEdition.org)	1.94	77	1.07	3.10	365	1.27	1.16*
1.6 Taking into consideration colleagues' opinions of it	3.10	77	0.88	2.97	363	1.05	0.13
1.7 Taking account of where source was obtained from (e.g. publisher's website, university library catalogue, search engine)	2.92	77	1.25	2.71	362	1.28	0.21
1.8 Checking the name of the publisher	3.36	77	1.12	2.70	364	1.23	0.66*
1.9 Checking to see how many times it has been downloaded/ accessed	2.26	77	1.01	2.55	365	1.61	0.29*
1.10 Checking whether author's country of affiliation is known for its research	2.35	77	1.14	2.55	366	1.13	0.2

* Significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, *** significant at $p < 0.05$

Question 2 (Table 7) asked respondents to rate their agreement with statements about the quality and trustworthiness of information sources on a scale of 5: strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neither agree nor disagree (3), agree (4), strongly agree (5).³

Unlike “younger researchers”, European doctoral students did not deem the journals' Impact Factor as a determining element for deciding what to read (question 2.2) as the “younger researchers” did, perhaps confirming that this kind of metric was not regarded as an objective way to measure the importance of a journal in the fields of social sciences and the humanities (Dorta-González & Dorta-González, 2013).

³ The description of the scale at p. 53 of Nicholas' article, which reverses the scale, is but a typo, as the correct order is given in the caption of Table 6.

Moreover, European doctoral students tended to disagree with the statement “when pressed for time, the ease of availability of a source over-takes considerations about its quality” (2.3), demonstrating more concern and attention towards quality and a better time management than “younger researchers”.

Table 7. Question 2: To what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements? (Mean rating, 1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree)

	EU doctoral students			Nicholas' "younger researchers"			d
	M	n	SD	M	n	SD	
2.1 Peer reviewed journals are the most trustworthy information source	3.86	77	0.85	3.85	364	0.99	0.01
2.2 The journal's Impact Factor is important for deciding what to read	2.58	77	1.16	3.37	365	1.13	0.79*
2.3 When pressed for time, the ease of availability of a source over-takes considerations about its quality	2.55	77	1.13	3.2	365	1.15	0.65*
2.4 If the information is not central to my research area, the ease of availability of a source is more important than its quality	2.73	77	1.07	2.95	363	1.18	0.22

* Significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, *** significant at $p < 0.05$

4.1.3 Dissemination and publishing

Although “younger researchers” were extracted from a pool of academics who published at least one article and, on the contrary, some of the European respondents in this research might have never published anything at the time when the web survey was conducted, it is still significant to understand what doctoral candidates think and comprehend of the most important activity carried out by scholars.

Question 3 (Table 9) asked to rate the importance of statements related to publishing outlets on a scale of not important (1), somewhat important (2), important (3), very important (4), extremely important (5).⁴

Peer review was once again the hallmark of quality for European doctoral students, who rated it as the most important attribute of an outlet as “younger researchers” did.

The ratings of the other statements show some differences for statements 3.3 and 3.4, which confirms that European doctoral students trusted more traditional publishers but also learned societies than “younger researchers”, while the latter attached more importance to an outlet having both online and printed versions than the European respondents (3.5).

Table 8. Question 3: As an author, how important are the following attributes of an outlet when deciding where to disseminate/publish your research work? (Mean rating, 1= Not important to 5= Extremely important)

	EU doctoral students			Nicholas' "younger researchers"			d
	M	n	SD	M	n	SD	
3.1 It is peer reviewed	4.31	77	0.75	3.85	363	1.14	0.46*
3.2 It is highly cited	3.83	77	0.97	3.66	364	1.16	0.17
3.3 It is published by a traditional scholarly publisher	3.56	77	1.02	3.29	363	1.17	0.27**
3.4 It is published by a society in my field	3.58	77	1.07	3.25	363	1.28	0.33***
3.5 It has both an online and a print version	2.55	77	1.33	2.96	363	1.46	0.41***
3.6 It is Open Access	3.04	77	1.26	2.82	362	1.23	0.22
3.7 It is based in a country known for the quality of its research	2.47	77	1.19	2.57	364	1.37	1.1

* Significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, *** significant at $p < 0.05$

Question 4 (Table 9) asked to rate the agreement with statements concerning the quality and trustworthiness of places to publish and disseminate research on a scale

⁴ The description of the scale at p. 54 of Nicholas' article, which reverses the scale, is but a typo, as the correct order is given in the caption of Table 7.

of strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neither agree nor disagree (3), agree (4), strongly agree (5).⁵

European doctoral students tended to agree with the sentence “people who don’t have tenure have to publish in good journals to build up a reputation” (4.1) even more than “younger researchers”, as probably their student status and the expected struggle to enter the job market worried them about their professional future and, not unpredictably, they trusted publications to be a gateway to academia.

Conference proceedings (4.3) were less important to European students, conceivably lacking much experience in participating and networking in events of this kind, than they were to “younger researchers”, as were the more informal outlets for dissemination such as personal websites (4.8) and blogs (4.9).

Finally, European doctoral students, in contrast with the opinion of the “younger researchers”, did not regard subject repositories of pre-prints (4.10) as particularly reliable dissemination channels. The responses to statements 4.3 and 4.10, however, reflect also the different composition of the two groups as they involve practices that are typical of scholars working in life and physical sciences.

Table 9. Question 4: To what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements concerning the quality and trustworthiness of places to publish/disseminate your research? (Mean rating, 1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree)

	EU doctoral students			Nicholas’ “younger researchers”			d
	M	n	SD	M	n	SD	
4.1 People who don’t have tenure have to publish in good journals to build up a reputation	4.00	77	1.06	3.72	365	1.09	0.28***
4.2 I publish in journals because a paper placed in a journal obtains a context, becomes part of a ‘conversation’	3.36	77	1.06	3.41	366	1.15	0.05
4.3 I tend to publish first in a conference proceedings, which is a good way to test the veracity of my ideas	3.00	77	1.27	3.28	360	1.30	0.28

⁵ The description of the scale at p. 55 of Nicholas’ article, which reverses the scale, is but a typo, as the correct order is given in the caption of Table 8.

4.4 I tend to publish first in a conference proceedings, because it is a reliable way to reach my target audiences	2.74	77	1.06	3.23	364	1.27	0.27*
4.5 Depositing a version of my published work in an institutional repository increases usage and thereby helps to build up my professional reputation among my peers	3.39	77	0.95	3.23	359	1.36	0.16
4.6 Depositing a version of my published work in an institutional repository increases citation and thereby helps to build up my professional reputation among my peers	3.29	77	0.93	3.14	362	1.39	0.15
4.7 I use social media (e.g. Twitter, blogs, social networks) to get out information about my research because it is a reliable way to reach my target audiences	2.96	77	1.45	2.84	362	1.26	0.12
4.8 My own website is central for ensuring the reliable dissemination of my work to my target audiences	2.26	77	1.11	2.73	360	1.50	0.47**
4.9 I tend to blog about the findings of my research, which is a good way to test the veracity of my ideas	1.88	77	1.08	2.72	360	1.36	0.84*
4.10 I tend to publish first in a subject repository (pre-publication database), such as ArXiv, PMC, RePEc, because it is a reliable way to reach wider audiences	2.05	77	1.09	2.56	360	1.47	0.51*

* Significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, *** significant at $p < 0.05$

4.1.4 Citing

According to Nicholas, citing to scholars is not as important as publishing in terms of career development. As true as this is to any researcher, proper citing is pivotal to any doctoral dissertation and is an essential skill to be developed in all postgraduate studies.

Question 5 (Table 10) asked to rate five citation practices on a scale of not characteristic (1), to very characteristic (5) of their disciplines. As explained by Nicholas, the question does not ask about individual practices in order not to trigger insincere answers, as some of the practices mentioned in the statements could be perceived as cheating.

Among the ten statements of question 5, only statement 5.10 concerning the practice of citing the published version of record, but reading another version found on the open web was rated differently by the two groups, as European students deemed it a practice more characteristic in their disciplines than “younger researchers”.

Table 10. Question 5: How characteristic of your discipline are each of the citing practices listed below? (Mean rating, 1= not characteristic to 5= very characteristic)

	EU doctoral students			Nicholas' "younger researchers"			d
	M	n	SD	M	n	SD	
5.1 Citing the most highly cited information sources	3.60	77	1.15	3.57	365	1.09	0.03
5.2 Citing the first information source published on a topic	3.22	77	1.08	3.22	366	1.15	0
5.3 Citing one's own work to improve one's citation ranking (e.g. H-Index)	2.56	77	1.18	2.86	360	1.30	0.3
5.4 Citing papers in the journal to which an article is submitted for publication to increase chances of acceptance	2.74	77	1.19	2.82	364	1.27	0.08
5.5 Citing papers mentioned by reviewers to increase chances of acceptance	3.36	77	1.28	3.06	359	1.36	0.3

5.6 Citing non-peer reviewed sources (e.g. personal correspondence, newspaper articles, blogs, tweets)	2.40	77	1.33	2.14	362	1.39	0.26
5.7 Citing a pre-print which has not yet been accepted by a journal	2.45	77	1.09	2.20	365	1.26	0.25
5.8 Citing sources disseminated with comments posted on a dedicated website (open peer review)	1.87	77	0.94	1.98	360	1.50	0.11
5.9 Citing, if possible, only sources published in developed countries	2.44	77	1.30	2.24	361	1.36	0.2
5.10 Citing the published version of record, but reading another version found on the open web	2.82	77	1.30	2.32	362	1.47	0.5***

* Significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, *** significant at $p < 0.05$

Question 6 (Table 11) asked to rate the agreement with statements about the quality and trustworthiness of the sources cited in a scale of strongly disagree (1), disagree (2) neither agree nor disagree (3), agree (4), strongly agree (5).⁶

For two statements in these questions (6.2 and 6.3), Nicholas' "younger researchers" agreed more than European students about not citing Open Access journals and on the importance of the Impact Factor.

Table 11. Question 6: To what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements concerning the quality and trustworthiness of the sources you cite? (Mean rating, 1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree)

	EU doctoral students			Nicholas' "younger researchers"			d
	M	n	SD	M	n	SD	
6.1 From a trust perspective I'm more easy-going in what I read than what I cite	3.73	77	1.17	3.65	362	1.10	0.08

⁶ The description of the scale at p. 57 of Nicholas' article, which reverses the scale, is but a typo, as the correct order is given in the caption of Table 9.

6.2 I don't cite articles published in Open Access journals because they are of low quality	1.66	77	0.79	2.34	361	1.19	0.68*
6.3 The journal Impact Factor is important for deciding what to cite	2.32	77	1.14	3.33	362	1.28	1.01*

* Significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, *** significant at $p < 0.05$

4.2 Discussion of Phase A

The aim of Phase A was twofold: to investigate the topic of trustworthiness in European doctoral students applied to the context of scholarly communication by way of a web survey and to compare findings of the same web survey with those of Nicholas et al. (2015) to ascertain the differences between those who in 2013 would have been called “younger researchers” and current doctoral students and whether the countries where these students were trained before starting their PhD affected the results.

4.2.1 Trustworthiness in European doctoral students

European doctoral students, unlike the group studied by George et al. (2006), in their answers indicated a familiarity with good practices in scholarly communication. When selecting the information needed for their research, for instance, they attributed the utmost importance to some characteristics that are inherent to publications, such as the abstract, the soundness of arguments and logic and the credibility of data. In addition to these features, the peer review process and the name of the publisher were to them trustworthy indicators of quality, while they were inclined to listen to their colleagues' opinions (as Vezzosi also found in her sample (2009)).

Nevertheless, there were noticeable shifts in their answers about reading and citing on the one hand and publishing on the other. When these students decided what to cite, they tended not to select only sources published in developed countries (Table 10, 5.9), and, in addition to this, the author's country of affiliation was unimportant (Table 6, 1.10). Moreover, when selecting material to read and use, many did not think that the Impact Factor was important in this process (Table 7, 2.2), nor was the number of times an item has been downloaded or accessed (Table 6, 1.9).

When they came to selecting their publishing outlets, however, they tended to prefer “traditional scholarly publishers” (Table 8, 3.3), hardly present in non-developed countries and, most importantly, they tended to give priority to highly cited outlets when deciding where to publish (Table 8, 3.2).

These inconsistencies might be explained by their expectations to join a competitive work environment and they attributed a great importance to publishing, as Jalongo et al. (2014) and Horta and Santos (2016) already evidenced. As far as dissemination and publishing are concerned, European doctoral students tended to think that publishing is pivotal for their reputation and success as academics, and they trusted journals and institutional repositories in their efforts to achieve this result.

As far as other tools of dissemination are concerned, conference proceedings, social media, personal websites, blogs and subject repositories were not particularly valued (Table 9, 4.3, 4.4, 4.7, 4.8, 4.9, 4.10). Open Access, on the other hand, was not mistrusted for both the activities of citing and publishing (Table 11, 6.2).

4.2.2 Comparison with Nicholas

As analysed in the first part of this Chapter (4.1.1), Nicholas’ “younger researchers” and the European doctoral students differed in age, experience, provenance and affiliation, and filled in this survey eight years apart. Nevertheless, the comparison between the responses given to the web survey by Nicholas’ “younger researchers” and the European doctoral students highlights remarkable similarities between these two groups. The few differences in their responses concern their academic affiliation, trust markers in scholarly communication, Open Access and institutional repositories and the dissemination of their work on informal web outlets.

Firstly, the divergences in the answers of European doctoral students and “younger researchers” can be explained by the absence of scholars in life and physical sciences among the students, all affiliated to disciplines pertaining to humanities and social sciences. “Younger researchers”, for example, relied more on conference proceedings to reach their target audiences (Table 9, 4.3), and they tended to publish first in a subject repository (Table 9, 4.10), two practices that are more established in the hard sciences. Conference proceedings might have been also less important to European students as they were conceivably lacking experience in participating and networking in events of this kind.

Secondly, European doctoral students were noticeably more doubtful about bibliometrics as tools to evaluate the information used in their research than “younger researchers” (Table 6, 1.9; Table 7, 2.2; Table 11, 6.3). This attitude reflects a certain scepticism towards bibliometrics which is due to the late and partial implementation of bibliometrics in the social sciences and humanities compared to its early development in STEM disciplines (Archambault & Larivière, 2010; van Raan, 2019). The distrust of doctoral students should also be put into the context of the scepticisms grown in recent years around the use of quantitative methods to evaluate research, especially in social sciences and humanities (Agate et al., 2020). If, on the one hand, Nicholas’ statement that young researchers “having to learn the scholarly ropes to ascend the career ladder, rely more on trust markers” is partially disproved by the results reported in the group of the European doctoral students, on the other hand, the dependence of the latter on the name and scholarly tradition of publishers, points in the opposite direction. To use again Nicholas’ words, the “badge of trust” for European doctoral students was the publisher, a more tangible entity to scholars in the social sciences than the volatile bibliometrics. Additionally, the publisher’s prestige is also a crucial building block, especially in the career of postdoctoral scholars in law, political science and history, as they tend to publish first the monograph derived from their thesis immediately after their doctorate.

Thirdly, European students expressed more trust in Open Access (Table 11, 6.2) and in the use of preprints (Table 10, 5.10). In the last two decades, not only have Open Access and institutional repositories enjoyed an exponential growth, but they also gained more approval among young scholars (Nassi Calò, 2015; Tenopir et al., 2017). Hence, the fact that the opinion of European students about Open Access and preprints was more positive than that of the “younger researchers” in 2013 was not unexpected.

Finally, an area presenting differences in these two groups is the dissemination of content through personal websites and blogs. Nicholas’ “younger researchers” exploited every outlet available to have their work published, such as repositories and proceedings, but also their own websites and blogs. In recent years, after all, the web opened up a vast array of possibilities for academics to engage with the public and to further their careers (Lupton et al., 2017). Despite the growth of free platforms providing these web services, and universities like the EUI equipping

themselves to deliver these tools (*EUI Personal Websites, 2021*), the European doctoral students did not attribute them much importance (Table 9, 4.8, 4.9).

This stand might not be surprising if one considers that keeping a personal website or blog is more common than it was in the past, but it is still a relatively infrequent practice among doctoral students, whose primary objective is to define and develop their theses and their skills as scholars, and might therefore lack the time and confidence to publicly divulge their work. This tendency was also reported by Delaney and Bates (2018) and reflects my personal experience of social media manager of the EUI Library, as in my daily work I do interact with many doctoral students on social media, who, nevertheless, seldom develop academic profiles and present their ideas on the web.

5 Phase B: Results and discussion

5.1 Results of Phase B

5.1.1 Interviews

A total of ten European students were interviewed. Six interviewees studied in one country before starting their doctorate and four studied in more than one country. To identify each interviewee, they were labelled with either an ISO 3166-1 alpha-3 three-letter country code, which stands for the one country where they studied (DNK, ESP, FRA, ITA, POL, PRT) or the letters MUL followed by a sequence number (MUL01, MUL02, MUL03, MUL04) if they studied in more than one country.

Specifically, the countries where the interviewees studied are Belarus, Belgium, Denmark, Germany, France, India, Italy, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Spain, The Netherlands and the United Kingdom. Five interviewees were from the Law Department, three from the History and Civilisation Department, one from the Economics Department and one from the Political and Social Sciences Department. Three interviewees were at least in their fourth year of doctoral programme, two in their third, four in their second, one in their first. Five interviewees were between 25 and 30 years of age, three of them 30 or older, and two were between 20 and 25 years old.

The interviews lasted from a minimum of 10 to a maximum of 28 minutes, for a total of 2 hours and 37 minutes. When transcribed, the length of the interviews amounted to about 21,800 words.

The theoretical model for the acquisitions of knowledge of scholarly communication and academic publishing (Figure 1) adds to Strauss and Corbin's archetype a connection between consequences and strategies, which is explained in paragraph 5.1.6.

Figure 1. Theoretical model for the acquisitions of knowledge of scholarly communication and academic publishing

5.1.2 Causal conditions

Four kinds of causal conditions determined particular phenomena associated to information literacy functional to scholarly communication. These causes were 1) the university's approach to information literacy 2) the supervisor's approach to information literacy 3) the student's approach to information literacy 4) the interviewees having had a research related job. Figure 2 below is a graphic representation of these four causal conditions.

Figure 2. Graphic representation of the causal conditions determining particular phenomena associated to information literacy functional to scholarly communication

The universities attended by interviewees before their doctorates approached information literacy mainly in three ways, namely prescriptive, passive and active. The prescriptive approach is that of university courses providing precise instructions on how to deal with reading and citing. For example, five interviewees mentioned mandatory reading lists for their courses and no encouragements to search for additional bibliography. In four cases students were also provided with written instructions on how to cite, like in the case of an interviewee, who, having studied in more than one country, noticed a difference: “in the UK they gave us a very precise a guide, so with all the indication about how to cite.” The passive approach is that of universities providing very little or no guidance in terms of information literacy, be it oriented towards citing, searching for bibliographic material or publishing, as for ITA, who noted the complete lack of courses in their former institution (“at the [name of university], there aren’t courses directly aimed at providing you with the instruments, the tools that you need”) as PRT did (“I wouldn’t say I had any specific course, like aiming at providing students with, with ways of finding bibliography or citations”). Finally, the active universities organise courses about information literacy and scholarly communication, as DNK (“I do know that the [name of university] have had a course where the purpose of it was to write an academic article”) and FRA (“then there were also some, some seminars like inside

of the regular curriculum, but they were taught by academics, and they also had academic writing”) both remark.

In addition to a general institutional approach, supervisors also had a pivotal role with their attitude which can also be classified as normative, as it was for PRT:

my supervisors, they were... sometimes they would just see an article that would be good for my master’s thesis, or for the research project I was working on and they would just email me that... the articles they thought could be beneficial for me

or active, as it was for FRA:

What we got from the seminars, and the relationships with your supervisors, was an assessment of journals in general, how you can extract things from them how they are to be evaluated, like which ones are good ones, and the not very renovated [renowned] ones which are not relevant.

During the doctorate, however, the role of the supervisor in the process of learning about scholarly communication reached a critical level like MUL02 articulated:

a big part is played by your relationship with your supervisors. [...] it’s essential, because I mean, then there are some supervisors that give you more guidance on this. Whereas the other supervisor, leave you a little bit more independent, because it’s something that you have to learn basically, always by yourself. [...] in that case, the relationship is, I mean, is really what makes the difference. And thanks to them, you can really learn also how to decide the which journals you should address which other you shouldn’t address.

The third condition was the student’s own attitude towards the help offered by the institutions, as often the students found too late about the training offered (DNK), they chose not to attend them (MUL04), or they were prevented by other commitments (MUL03).

Finally, research related jobs had a significant impact on the phenomenon explained below. A few interviewees held paid jobs in different capacities, for example as research assistants, museum staff, staff in governmental bodies, they interned in law firms or governmental bodies or they simply held positions in student law reviews. In most cases, as DNK put it, these jobs were the proper “introduction to

academia”, in the sense that they learned “much more from my research position than from my actual classes”. These posts, held whilst studying or in between degrees, were often a hands-on training on bibliography search (MUL02: “they helped us understand how to search for bibliographies”), citation and plagiarism (MUL03: “the Law Review would run sessions on citation and plagiarism. Our university wasn’t doing that separately”), and publishing, as for MUL04:

when I was an academic assistant, there was a certain insistence on publishing certain things”; MUL02: “the director of the research centre kept saying, as you should ever look at this list, because it’s important, you should target all with a journal [...].

5.1.3 Phenomenon resulting from causal conditions

The phenomenon stemming from the causal conditions described above is knowledge (in various degrees) of scholarly communication and how to publish.

Interviewees assessed and expressed their competences in scholarly communication in various ways along different stages of their career. Expertise on scholarly communication was articulated in assertions about Open Access, as for example with MUL01 stating that “in Eastern Europe, I have to say, open access [...] before the very word Open Access was coined, Open Access was already an option [...] a regular option.” Opinions on bibliometrics were also voiced, and remarkably quite polarised, as for instance DNK dismissed them: “I don’t think that they are able to go through the chapters and edited books that well”; while FRA recognises their worth: “I think it somehow makes sense what they say, that if people read your research, actually, it does not only feel good, but [...] actually somehow that something that values research afterwards.”

In addition to these topics, the interviewees’ knowledge of some publishing dynamics often surfaced with phrases on how scholars cite each other: “everyone cites their friends, right?” (DNK); on the value of publishing; “it is also important to publish. It’s also because you want to engage with other people. And this is also very good feedback for yourself” (FRA); on the assessment of journals: “but you know that if something is published in the [name of journal], then it has a certain quality that probably some obscure journal doesn’t have, right?”; on the bias towards journals not published in developed countries: “I think there’s a certain bias unnecessarily and prejudice there” (MUL04). Finally, interviewees demonstrated

some understanding of academic publishing, for instance on how early career scholars could tackle it (MUL03: “it’s difficult for early career researchers to make inroads into some very conventional, long standing journals”; MUL02: “I basically chose journals that I like, where I know that there are people who I’m interested in”).

In many cases interviewees could credit the doctoral programme with the acquisition of this kind of knowledge, therefore implying that their previous education did not provide them with it, for instance MUL03: “these are all conversations I’ve managed to have only after I came to the EUI”. Among the notions listed in this category, there are the concepts of journal assessment and journal prestige, Open Access, peer review and in general how to publish, with a few interviewees having first-hand experience. There are cases, however, in which the faults of the doctoral programme in this context were highlighted. MUL04 stated that “there’s no real training on how to publish or how you should publish”, echoed by POL: “I don’t think I gained much more knowledge. I think [publishing] is still before me.”

5.1.4 Context in which the phenomenon developed and intervening conditions

In addition to direct causal conditions, the phenomenon described above took place in a variety of contexts, which had an indirect influence on them: 1) the subject area 2) the national publishing culture 3) the supervisor’s attitude to publishing and scholarly communication 4) the university’s attitude to publishing and scholarly communication 5) the university’s lack of resources.

The primary contextual dynamic which shaped the acquisition of information literacy for these students is the subject area in which they work, as each one has specific scholarly communication dynamics. The interviewees kept referring to the disciplinary specificities of their fields, for example DNK: “we also publish differently, I think, like in, in law, at least, we do a lot of the edited volumes”; ESP: “in economics in academia, I think it’s kind of hard to publish”; MUL01, a history researcher: “I have heard that in western museums, research fellows are pressed to publish in like... I never heard that, the impact and the... all these metrics are used to assess work outcomes of research fellows even in western museums”; MUL04, a law researcher:

I think in my specific field, I do, EU law, especially empirical studies, and thankfully, I think being cited is important, but not that much, because there are not so many people... it’s ten people, and I think we cite each other.

Despite their affiliation with an international institution such as the EUI at the time of the interviews, some doctoral candidates bore in mind some governmental regulations for quality assessment of the activities carried out by universities and research institutes recipients of public funding. In Italy, for instance, these protocols affect directly the choice of the publishing outlets and of the journals where to publish, which are classified according to their reliability. Scholars are rewarded in competitions for the public sector whenever they publish articles, for instance, in a “class A” journal, as MUL02 learnt from their job as research assistant:

then being Italian [...] there is also another issue that sometimes we should consider, but perhaps it's too early for me. And it's the... How is it called? The *abilitazione nazionale* [national qualifying exam to access tenured teaching positions] [...] and you should also pay a little bit of attention to the... to the journals that they list in that specific academic discipline, because otherwise [...] it might be difficult [...] to be successful in the *abilitazione*. And, and then I mean, in many universities in Italy, and also, they [have] internal list with A, B, C journals.

Something similar happens in Belarus, as MUL01 testified: “those who do their PhD in Belarus are pressed to publish only in journals which are certified by the Belarusian national authorities as journals.”

Another contextual factor to be taken into account is that of the supervisor's attitude to publishing and information literacy, this figure to be intended here as both the academic supervisor and the job's supervisor. DNK for example, had a master's degree supervisor who was knowledgeable about American law review platforms for article submission and took the time to explain how they work:

my supervisor at the time did suggest I tried the American [...] like a scholarly, scholarly web thing or something where you serve it this way, you will upload your paper to this service. And then I think, a bunch of American law review journals, they sort of bid on it or something. So, he was very, he recommended a bit, told me a bit about how that process was, how to improve your paper for work towards publishing in American law journals. But I never actually did it. But he was very, he was very into that style.

PRT had fond memories of a PI with whom they worked, as this person was particularly attentive and willing to share valuable advice:

he was also explaining me... [...] he was publishing, like, three, four times a year, [...] and he was always telling me like: now they're rejected, and this was because of this, [...] I can't put [it] in my social media because it's not Open Access. And then... so I got more aware of how it works.

In addition to the supervisor's attitude, each university may have a specific attitude to scholarly communication. The competitive university attended by ITA, for example, despite pushing its students towards an academic career thus creating "a sense of social pressure towards doing a PhD", and despite encouraging "autonomous research from the first year", it did not provide any information literacy training, and, on the contrary, "you are expected to learn how to swim in these difficult waters [...] and this, like, Darwinian selection method are... should be discussed better." In other cases, other university environments were perceived by interviewees as particularly lenient or strict towards practices like citing and plagiarism, and in a peculiar case (FRA) both:

this was this Franco German campus, so basically one third of the seminars was taught in English, one taught in German and one taught French. Very interesting to see the different approaches to citing. French professors, they didn't really care. And German professors were very much about citing.

Finally, the lack of resources in the university library negatively influenced the development of DNK's skills in information literacy:

we have a humanities faculties library, so it wasn't really even a law section. [...] And so that was quite a way to sort of see this, like, grand scale of academic publications within a field was much more difficult.

5.1.5 Strategies for managing phenomenon

As most interviewees admitted not having received during their master's degree the information literacy training which is necessary to understand the world of scholarly communication, when asked how they acquired this kind of knowledge, they shed light on their alternative strategies, mainly 1) self-teaching 2) learning from peers and networking.

Practices of self-teaching were widespread among interviewees especially when it came to searching for material to read. Those who were not directly told what to read, either by way of reading lists or by their supervisor, talked about being left

completely on their own (MUL02), about “an intuitive start” (DNK), or they admitted learning by themselves (ITA), learning by doing (MUL04), googling (PRT) and searching autonomously the databases available at the library (POL). Many followed citation chains (DNK, ESP, PRT), and eventually only following the trail of the most prestigious journals (ESP). During the doctoral programme, self-teaching was pivotal in learning how to publish for MUL02, who tried to publish a journal article and benefited from a trial-and-error method:

it was like rejected first and then I tried again. And at this time, I mean, the situation improved a little bit because I lowered, let's say, also my ambitions, sending to the less ambitious, sending it to a less ambitious journal.

Learning about scholarly communication from peers was the default information literacy for some interviewees who were not offered courses by their university such as POL, who actively asked them for help: “I was asking some earlier colleagues, for advice, or recommendation.” POL also stated that “I was lucky enough to have friends and some young scholars that I communicated with, and this was more like some peer education and some giving feedback and reading together and so on.”

ITA had an analogous experience:

surely what I learned, everything, almost, I learned from my peers, maybe the ones who were a little bit older than me, and then that showed me, explained me how to do your research.

Knowledge about academic publishing was also acquired from peers by POL: “I got some advice from elder colleagues, like, for example, where to publish, how much to publish, when and so on. And this is, I see that this is not easily available knowledge”.

5.1.6 Consequences

The various degrees of knowledge in scholarly communication and academic publishing have substantial effects on young scholars, namely 1) publishing/not publishing 2) experiencing difficulties in publishing 3) self-awareness of one's skills 4) commitment to certain publishing practices.

In research institutions such as the EUI it is common to find doctoral students with wide-ranging experiences of publishing. Out of ten interviewees, four had already produced at least one academic publication. MUL03, for example, had an

impressive record of four publications, for which they detailed how they chose where to publish, that is through networking and by targeting journals keen to publish early career scholars:

so, two of those publications came through conferences that I was doing. So, at the conference, [they] were saying, you know, we'll create a working paper series out of this, or we'll create a book out of this, which is what they ended up doing. One was, like, word of mouth. So, somebody was interning [...] he ended up being editor of a Springer encyclopaedia. And he asked me if I would write for it. So, two of the publications that I've done, which were not solicited publications, they were two journals that I know, are very, very keen on publishing early career scholars.

This interviewee displayed an uncommon knowledge of academic publishing for such a young scholar, which was fed by a well-rounded training in the three countries where they studied before starting their doctoral programme.

Most interviewees who already published or were attempting to publish agreed in finding this experience arduous, as MUL04 said: "I think I became aware that it was more difficult than I thought". The difficulties in publishing and the subsequent frustration are themselves, however, opportunities to learn, even when witnessing the struggle of peers, according to MUL04:

[during the doctoral programme] you have all these people that are constantly sending papers to all these journals and constantly getting rejections and getting these R&R [revise and resubmit]. And that I never knew. So, I do think I have learned a lot.

One of the direct consequences of the interviewees' troubles with this process is their self-perception as "lazy" (ESP) or "slow" (MUL02). Being in a research institute does not help POL, who revealed that "even as such, international, open minded place as the EU it's not something that it's obvious. And I think that people struggle with this."

Being confronted with the experience of peers and having gained knowledge about scholarly communication and academic publishing, some interviewees expressed self-awareness about their skills, like POL and MUL04: "I don't, I still don't know sometimes, [...] how you assess where to send things". Some interviewees regret

not having been trained more, like ESP: “I guess it would have been useful to have more guidance on this.”

Finally, having been exposed to certain practices during pre-doctoral studies, resulted in a strong commitment to the same practices, as it was the case of MUL01 and Open Access:

I have learned more about publishing already. Already before coming to EUI I... Yes, because publishing [...] not just Open Access, but I was publishing in the Creative Commons license and I only became stronger in my case, [...] I became fortified in my commitment to further publish in... under this license and to find my find journals which will publish like this.

It is only natural to add to the theoretical model for the acquisitions of knowledge of scholarly communication and academic publishing (Figure 1) a link between consequences and strategies, as the absence of publications, the self-awareness and the difficulties experienced in publishing trigger once again those strategies adopted when the knowledge of scholarly communication and academic publishing does not suffice reach the goals of the interviewees. As young scholars, the interviewees felt the pressure of a competitive environment, for instance ESP:

But I really need to do it because it's affecting my CV. So, whenever I'm just asking for money or whatever, for scholarships, the one thing that they always tell me is that I should have this research papers published.

Consequently, they took actions to get themselves out of the impasse, like POL: “and I also struggled to get this information, like what to publish of your work and when and where. I'm trying, I was trying to get some courses.”

5.2 Discussion of Phase B

The aim of Phase B was to investigate the correlation between the assessment of trustworthiness in doctoral students and their competences in information literacy.

The theoretical model developed in the previous chapter (5.1.1) illustrates the process of acquisition of information literacy in relation to scholarly communication and academic publishing. Unfortunately, for most of the interviewees, this process was arduous, mainly because their previous institutions, together with their past

supervisors, held a passive or merely prescriptive approach to information literacy and, in addition to this, knowledge concerning academic publishing was seldom tackled during the master's degree programmes. Most of the participants, therefore, recognise the value of the training sessions offered during their doctoral programme, much like the graduate students in the study by Owens and Manolovitz, (2021), and regret not attending any similar training earlier in their education.

Their partial unfamiliarity with these practices could explain why doctoral students, in their selection of what to read, trust more those elements, which are inherent to publications, rather than other external sources of information, for example indexing bodies. In addition to this, their reliance on the traditional peer review process and on prestigious and traditional publishers could derive from a prescriptive kind of education, in which it is easier to give clear-cut tools, albeit not too sophisticated, to sift through large bibliographies. Besides, the inconsistencies highlighted in their answers, especially as far as bibliometrics are concerned, might also be a symptom of inadequate knowledge of scholarly communication.

Another remarkable aspect of the results obtained with grounded theory analysis is the possibility of discerning the coping strategies employed in order to compensate for the absence of training. Those who felt completely left on their own, for instance, turned to their peers, a behaviour that was observed also among doctoral students (Vezzosi, 2009). Several doctoral candidates among the interviewees, however, encountered another major causal condition for the acquisition of information literacy, i.e. they held a research-related job. Practical experience holds a degree of efficiency in providing students with information and skills that is unrivalled, as it transforms implicit knowledge into explicit information (Badenhorst & Xu, 2016). Often the students mentioned these jobs together with senior researchers in supervisory roles, pressed by the prospect of achieving goals and meet deadlines and willing to explain and instruct them on the nuts and bolts of academic publishing.

As it was the case with Phase A of this research, also in Phase B the results are hardly influenced by the countries where the doctoral candidates studied if not for the national publishing culture, which in turn is determined by the laws and regulations in place to assess those institutes recipient of public funding. On the contrary, the profile of the single universities or institutions in which the interviewees studied for their master's degree and the ensuing approach to information literacy

and attitude to academic publishing and scholarly communication is crucial in determining what kind of knowledge their students acquire. This observation aligns with previous research conducted on European national higher education systems in relation to European policy, which highlighted an extreme diversity among and within countries (Huisman & van Vught, 2009).

By comparing the interviewees, something else becomes clear. Participants who studied in more than one country before their doctorates were more aware and receptive of dynamics in scholarly communication and sometimes held knowledge which was more well-rounded than that developed by their one-country counterparts, as by default, “multinational” students had been influenced by the different approaches adopted by their universities and supervisors and by several different contextual conditions. Conversely, those who studied in one country sometimes expressed more polarised opinions (see for instance FRA and DNK’s perspectives on bibliometrics, despite their affiliation to the same discipline). It is known that the Erasmus student mobility programme has a positive impact in terms of graduate employability (Di Pietro, 2015; Bryła, 2015; Soares & Mosquera, 2020; Iriondo, 2020), but there is no focus or even statistics available on general international mobility, i.e. the effects of European mobility on students who obtained their degrees in different countries (Teichler, 2017). Only very recently Gregor Schäfer proposed a definition of “mobility capital” of European higher education (Schäfer, 2020a) and investigated spatial mobility and the perception of career development for social sciences and humanities doctoral candidates (Schäfer, 2020b).

Finally, the case of MUL01 and their firm commitment to Open Access seem to confirm the favourable attitude of the European doctoral students towards this practice. In the interviews, nonetheless, MUL01’s is a unique case of explicit devotion towards Open Access that derives from their education, their training, and the national context in which they took place. As Open Access is a relatively young movement in academia, there is yet no research dedicated to the impact that it has had on master’s degree and doctoral students, but the case of MUL01 seems suggest that an early exposure to it might help in forming scholar devoted to this cause.

6 Conclusions and recommendations

This research project focussed on two main aims (Chapter 3):

- A. To investigate the trustworthiness of European doctoral students in the context of scholarly communication and to determine the degree of correlation between this group and the “younger researchers” examined by Nicholas et al. (2015).
- B. To explore the correlation between the information literacy competences acquired by European doctoral student during their previous education and their trustworthiness in the context of scholarly communication.

These broad aims encompassed four specific objectives, established in chapter 1.2 ((a), (b), (c) and (d)). This chapter will summarise findings, offer conclusions and suggest developments for future research (objective (e)).

6.1 Summary of findings

Objective (a)

The literature review pointed out how the issue of trust in scholarly communication has gained relevance in the literature of the last twenty years, almost without any specific focus, however, on doctoral students. This population of scholars is developing a strained relationship with scholarly communication because of its increased need to publish, brought about by a fiercely competitive job market for early career scholars.

Although the information literacy provided to and developed by doctoral students has been researched, the influence of the training received at master’s level and the role of information literacy in the future professional life of PhD students were only addressed on a speculative level.

Objective (b)

European doctoral students are, after all, scholars in the making, and, as such, they attributed great importance to publishing as a means to become established academics. Their main indicators of trust outside the inherent characteristics of scholarly publications are the name of the publisher and the peer review process.

Their inexperience also emerged in some double standards, especially concerning selecting material to read and cite on the one hand and disseminating their own

research on the other. They expressed distrust towards bibliometrics but gave priority to highly cited outlets when deciding where to publish, and they did not deem relevant the country of provenance of an author or a source while they wished to publish mainly for traditional scholarly publishers.

This group was also inclined to listen to their colleagues' opinions and, notably, to disdain web tools of dissemination such as social media, personal websites and blogs.

Finally, Open Access was trusted for both the activities of citing and publishing.

Objective (c)

The two web surveys were conducted eight years apart, a significant amount of time in which much has changed in scholarly communication, and, in addition to this, the average age, the experience, the disciplinary affiliation and the provenance of the participants in the two groups were very different. Despite these dissimilarities, the results of this web survey and those of Nicholas et al. (2015) are strikingly similar. The few differences concern mainly five aspects.

The academic affiliation to hard science played a role for about half of the “younger researchers”, who relied more on conference proceedings and subject repositories than the European doctoral students. In regard to trust markers, the doctoral students tended to be more sceptical towards bibliometrics than “younger researchers”, while they gave more importance to the name of the publisher. European students expressed more trust in Open Access and in the use of preprints but, surprisingly, they are not particularly interested in using websites and blogs for dissemination like the “younger researchers” did.

Objective (d)

A theoretical model was developed to illustrate the process of acquisition of information literacy in relation to scholarly communication and academic publishing. This learning process was laborious for most participants, because the universities they attended before starting their doctorates and their master's degree supervisors typically held a passive or prescriptive approach to information literacy and academic publishing was seldom tackled during the master's degree programmes. The unfamiliarity with these practices can explain the doctoral students' distrust towards those quality indicators that are not inherent to publications and their

reliance on the peer review process and on prestigious and traditional publishers. The model suggests, however, that when students are exposed early on to publishing practices (such as Open Access), they tend to be committed to them in the long term. Coping strategies employed to compensate for the absence of training were identified, such as turning to peers for help. Moreover, the theoretical model revealed that holding a research related job and with the practical experience gained via this extra-curricular activity is a greater causal condition leading to the acquisition of knowledge than the university's and the supervisor's approach to information literacy.

Besides the theoretical model, it was noted how students who took advantage of the European international mobility and studied in several countries before starting their doctorate held a better knowledge of scholarly communication and of academic publishing than their one-country counterparts.

Finally, as well as in Phase A, in Phase B the results were not influenced as much by the countries of provenance of the interviewees as by the approach of the single universities or institutions in which they studied for their master's degree.

6.2 Limitations

Time and financial limitations constrained the data that I was able to collect for Phase A of this research. The web survey was sent to a subgroup of doctoral students in the European Higher Education Area, coming from half of the countries belonging to the EHEA and not affiliated to STEM disciplines, hence providing a limited overview of European doctoral students. In addition to this, only 12.26% of those invited filled in the web survey therefore weakening the strength of the conclusions that could be drawn, and those who did respond indicated a wide variety of countries where they studied before starting their doctorate, thus making the analysis of the results by country not possible. Finally, the comparison of results between this web survey and those of Nicholas was limited by the unavailability of Nicholas' original dataset, which would have allowed to disaggregate the answers given by STEM scholars from those of the HSS scholars, therefore enabling a better comparison.

In Phase B, limitations were imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, which allowed only online interviewing with its issues of limited interaction and technical difficulties.

6.3 Recommendations for future research

In Phase A, this research was concerned with trustworthiness in reading, citing and publishing in relation to European doctoral students, even though the limitations highlighted in the paragraph above prevented me from encompassing the whole EHEA area and all the disciplines. Investigating further the mindset and the opinions of European doctoral students, researchers at the earliest stage of their career in an ever-evolving continent subject to many social dynamics concerning integration, can shed light on the state of doctoral studies.

The state of information literacy in the EHEA should also be at the centre of future research, as there is no updated and comprehensive investigation of the universities' approach to this crucial matter, only literature reviews with a focus on Europe and proposed frameworks for policy analysis (Virkus, 2003; Basili, 2011; Virkus, 2012; Virkus, 2013). Although limited and explorative, the research conducted in Phase B of this dissertation clearly shows that the training provided to postgraduate students affects their success and wellbeing as future scholars, and therefore an investigation on a large scale with clear recommendation for practice could make the difference in the future of European academia.

Finally, a separate enquiry should concern the consequences of Brexit on European academic mobility and knowledge of scholarly communication. Given that a considerable portion of the multinational students who took part in this research gained at least one degree in the United Kingdom, and taking into account the attention given to information literacy in British universities, it is legitimate to wonder if the foreseen decrease of European students in this country will have an impact also on the skills and knowledge of European doctoral candidates.

Word count: 14,526

7 Bibliography

- Agate, N., Kennison, R., Konkiel, S., Long, C. P., Rhody, J., Sacchi, S., & Weber, P. (2020). The transformative power of values-enacted scholarship. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 7(1), 165.
<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-00647-z>
- Anderson, R. (2018). *Scholarly communication: What everyone needs to know*. Oxford University Press.
- Archambault, É., & Larivière, V. (2010). The limits of bibliometrics for the analysis of the social sciences and humanities literature. *World Social Science Report 2009/2010*.
- Badenhorst, C., & Xu, X. (2016). Academic publishing: Making the implicit explicit. *Publications*, 4(3), 24. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications4030024>
- Basili, C. (2011). A framework for analyzing and comparing information literacy policies in European countries. *Library Trends*, 60(2), 395–418.
<https://doi.org/doi:10.1087/20140206>
- Ben-Nun, P. (2011). Respondent fatigue. In *Encyclopedia of Survey Research Methods*. SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963947>
- Björk, B.-C., & Holmström, J. (2006). Benchmarking scientific journals from the submitting author's viewpoint. *Learned Publishing*, 19(2), 147–155.
<https://doi.org/10.1087/095315106776387002>
- Joint declaration of the European Ministers of Education convened in Bologna on 19 June 1999, (1999). http://www.magna-charta.org/resources/files/BOLOGNA_DECLARATION.pdf
- Bryła, P. (2015). The impact of international student mobility on subsequent employment and professional career: A large-scale survey among Polish

- former Erasmus students. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 176, 633–641. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.521>
- Catling, J., Mason, V., & Upton, D. (2009). Quality is in the eye of the beholder? An evaluation of impact factors and perception of journal prestige in the UK. *Scientometrics*, 81(2), 333–345. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-009-2124-1>
- Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches* (2nd ed). SAGE Publications.
- Delaney, G., & Bates, J. (2018). How can the university library better meet the information needs of research students? Experiences from Ulster University. *New Review of Academic Librarianship*, 24(1), 63–89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13614533.2017.1384267>
- Di Pietro, G. (2015). Do study abroad programs enhance the employability of graduates? *Education Finance and Policy*, 10(2), 223–243.
- Dialsingh, I. (2011). Mail survey. In *Encyclopedia of Survey Research Methods* (pp. 445–447). SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963947>
- Dodds, S., & Hess, A. C. (2020). Adapting research methodology during COVID-19: Lessons for transformative service research. *Journal of Service Management*, 32(2), 203–217. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOSM-05-2020-0153>
- Dorta-González, P., & Dorta-González, M. I. (2013). Comparing journals from different fields of science and social science through a JCR subject categories normalized impact factor. *Scientometrics*, 95(2), 645–672. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-012-0929-9>
- EUI Community—Formerly EUI newcomers 2.0*. (2021). Facebook.com. <https://www.facebook.com/groups/1701007826892534/>

EUI personal websites. (2021, January). EUI Personal Websites.

<https://me.eui.eu/>

European Education Area. (2018). Education and Training - European

Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/education/education-in-the-eu/european-education-area_en

European Higher Education Area and Bologna Process. (2021). European Higher

Education Area. <https://ehea.info/>

European University Association. (2005). *Doctoral programmes for the European knowledge society: Report on the EUA doctoral programmes project 2004-2005.*

<https://eua.eu/downloads/publications/doctoral%20programmes%20for%20the%20european%20knowledge%20society%20results%20of%20eua%20doctoral%20programme.pdf>

European University Association. (2010). *Salzburg II Recommendations-European universities' achievements since 2005 in implementing the Salzburg Principles.*

<https://eua.eu/downloads/publications/salzburg%20ii%20recommendations%202010.pdf>

European University Association. (2016). *Taking Salzburg forward:*

Implementation and new challenges.

European University Institute. (2020). *Convention setting up a European*

University Institute as revised by the 1992 amending Convention. European University Institute.

<https://www.eui.eu/Documents/AboutEUI/Convention/Consolidated-Convention-following-UK-exit.pdf>

- Explanatory memorandum to the European University Institute (EU exit) regulations 2019.* (2019). GOV.UK.
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5c6c3423e5274a72be398f0c/EUI_EM_FINAL.pdf
- George, C., Bright, A., Hurlbert, T., Linke, E. C., St. Clair, G., & Stein, J. (2006). Scholarly use of information: Graduate students' information seeking behaviour. *Information Research: An International Electronic Journal*, 11(4).
<https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1104651>
- Gibson, W., & Brown, A. (2009). *Working with Qualitative Data*. SAGE Publications, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9780857029041>
- Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. L. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Aldine Pub. Co.
- Han, J. (2012). Information literacy challenges for Chinese PhD students in Australia: A biographical study. *Journal of Information Literacy*, 6(1).
<https://doi.org/10.11645/6.1.1603>
- Horta, H., & Santos, J. M. (2016). The impact of publishing during PhD studies on career research publication, visibility, and collaborations. *Research in Higher Education*, 57(1), 28–50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11162-015-9380-0>
- Howlett, M. (2021). Looking at the 'field' through a Zoom lens: Methodological reflections on conducting online research during a global pandemic. *Qualitative Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794120985691>
- Hughes, J. (2012). *SAGE Internet research methods*. SAGE Publications Ltd.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446263327>
- Hugick, L., & Best, J. (2011). Questionnaire Length. In *Encyclopedia of Survey Research Methods* (p. 660). SAGE Publications, Inc.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963947>

- Huisman, J., & van Vught, F. (2009). Diversity in European higher education: Historical trends and current policies. In F. van Vught (Ed.), *Mapping the Higher Education Landscape: Towards a European Classification of Higher Education* (pp. 17–37). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-2249-3_2
- Ince, S., Hoadley, C., & Kirschner, P. A. (2019). The role of libraries in teaching doctoral students to become information-literate researchers: A review of existing practices and recommendations for the future. *Information and Learning Sciences*, *120*(3/4), 158–172. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ILS-07-2018-0058>
- Iriondo, I. (2020). Evaluation of the impact of Erasmus study mobility on salaries and employment of recent graduates in Spain. *Studies in Higher Education*, *45*(4), 925–943. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2019.1582011>
- Jalongo, M. R., Boyer, W., & Ebbeck, M. (2014). Writing for scholarly publication as “tacit knowledge”: A qualitative focus group study of doctoral students in education. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, *42*(4), 241–250. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-013-0624-3>
- Jamali, H. R., Nicholas, D., Watkinson, A., Herman, E., Tenopir, C., Levine, K., Allard, S., Christian, L., Volentine, R., Boehm, R., & Nichols, F. (2014). How scholars implement trust in their reading, citing and publishing activities: Geographical differences. *Library & Information Science Research*, *36*(3–4), 192–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lisr.2014.08.002>
- Koler-Povh, T., & Turk, Ž. (2020). Information literacy of doctoral students in engineering and the librarian’s role. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, *52*(1), 27–39. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000618767726>

- Kwan, B. S. C. (2010). An investigation of instruction in research publishing offered in doctoral programs: The Hong Kong case. *Higher Education*, 59(1), 55–68. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-009-9233-x>
- Lewis-Beck, M., Bryman, A., & Futing Liao, T. (2004). Comparative research. In *The SAGE encyclopedia of social science research methods*. SAGE Publications. <https://methods.sagepub.com/reference/the-sage-encyclopedia-of-social-science-research-methods>
- Lupton, D., Mewburn, I., & Thomson, P. (2017). The digital academic: Identities, context and politics. In *The digital academic: Critical perspectives on digital technologies in higher education*. Routledge.
- Malingre, M.-L., & Serres, A. (2011). Une culture informationnelle commune aux doctorants ? In C. Denecker & M. Durand-Barthez (Eds.), *La formation des doctorants à l'information scientifique et technique* (pp. 53–67). Presses de l'enssib. <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.pressesenssib.945>
- Manzari, L. (2013). Library and information science journal prestige as assessed by library and information science faculty. *The Library Quarterly*, 83(1), 42–60. <https://doi.org/10.1086/668574>
- Moore, M., & Singley, E. (2019). Understanding the information behaviors of doctoral students: An exploratory study. *Portal: Libraries and the Academy*, 19(2), 279–293. <https://doi.org/10.1353/pla.2019.0016>
- Moore, N. (2006). *How to do research: A practical guide to designing and managing research projects* (3., rev. ed). Facet.
- Nagano, R. L., & Spiczéné Bukovszki, E. (2016). Doctoral students' perspectives on academic publishing. *EduLingua*, 2(1), 1–14.
- Nassi Calò, L. (2015, September 17). The favourable perception of open access increases among researchers. *SciELO in Perspective*.

<https://blog.scielo.org/en/2015/09/17/the-favourable-perception-of-open-access-increases-among-researchers/#.YOcwuugzaUk>

- Nicholas, D., Jamali, H. R., Herman, E., Watkinson, A., Abrizah, A., Rodríguez-Bravo, B., Boukacem-Zeghmouri, C., Xu, J., Świgoń, M., & Polezhaeva, T. (2020). A global questionnaire survey of the scholarly communication attitudes and behaviours of early career researchers. *Learned Publishing*, 33(3), 198–211. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1286>
- Nicholas, D., Jamali, H. R., Watkinson, A., Herman, E., Tenopir, C., Volentine, R., Allard, S., & Levine, K. (2015). Do younger researchers assess trustworthiness differently when deciding what to read and cite and where to publish? *International Journal of Knowledge Content Development & Technology*, 5(2), 45–63. <https://doi.org/10.5865/IJKCT.2015.5.2.045>
- Nicholas, D., Watkinson, A., Volentine, R., Allard, S., Levine, K., Tenopir, C., & Herman, E. (2014). Trust and authority in scholarly communications in the light of the digital transition: Setting the scene for a major study. *Learned Publishing*, 27(2), 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.1087/20140206>
- Niederl, A., Bonaccorsi, A., Lepori, B., Brandt, T., De Filippo, D., & Schmoch, U. (2014). Mapping the European higher education landscape: New insights from the EUMIDA project. In A. Bonaccorsi, *Knowledge, Diversity and Performance in European Higher Education* (pp. 13–46). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783472000.00007>
- Nylander, E., & Hjort, M. (2020). Information literacies of PhD students: A hermeneutic dialectic study within the health sciences. *New Review of Academic Librarianship*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13614533.2020.1819353>
- Owens, E. E., & Manolovitz, T. (2021). Scholarly communication outside the R1: Measuring faculty and graduate student knowledge and Interest at a

- doctoral/professional university. *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication*, 9(1), 2413. <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2413>
- Øyen, E. (Ed.). (1990). *Comparative methodology: Theory and practice in international social research*. SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Oyewo, E. A., & Umoh Uwem, S. (2016). Information literacy, research, scholarship and publication: Comparative of PhD students in Nigerian and South African universities. *Revista Brasileira de Planejamento e Desenvolvimento*, 5(3), 458–474.
- Prøitz, T. S., & Wittek, L. (2020). New directions in doctoral programmes: Bridging tensions between theory and practice? *Teaching in Higher Education*, 25(5), 560–578. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2019.1577813>
- Ragin, C. C. (2006). How to lure analytic social science out of the doldrums: Some lessons from comparative research. *International Sociology*, 21(5), 633–646. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0268580906067834>
- Schäfer, G. (2020a). Accumulation of mobility capital over the life course of mobile doctoral candidates. *Applied Mobilities*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23800127.2020.1716452>
- Schäfer, G. (2020b). Spatial mobility and the perception of career development for social sciences and humanities doctoral candidates. *Studies in Continuing Education*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0158037X.2020.1826919>
- SCONUL Working Group on Information Literacy. (2011). *The SCONUL Seven Pillars of Information Literacy: Core model for higher education*. SCONUL. sconul.ac.uk/sites/default/files/documents/coremodel.pdf
- Serres, A. (n.d.). *FORMADOCT: A propos: Historique du projet*. Retrieved 19 July 2020, from <https://formadoct.doctorat-bretagne.fr/c.php?g=491541&p=3362644>

- Soares, M. E., & Mosquera, P. (2020). Linking development of skills and perceptions of employability: The case of Erasmus students. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 33(1), 2769–2786.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2019.1697330>
- Speier, C., Palmer, J., Wren, D., & Hahn, S. (1999). Faculty perceptions of electronic journals as scholarly communication: A question of prestige and legitimacy. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 50(6), 537–543. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-4571\(1999\)50:6%3C537::AID-ASI9%3E3.0.CO;2-6](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-4571(1999)50:6%3C537::AID-ASI9%3E3.0.CO;2-6)
- Taylor, L., & Willett, P. (2017). Comparison of US and UK rankings of LIS journals. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*.
- Teichler, U. (2017). Internationally mobile academics: Concept and findings in Europe. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 7(1), 15–28.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/21568235.2017.1254921>
- Tenopir, C., Dalton, E., Christian, L., Jones, M., McCabe, M., Smith, M., & Fish, A. (2017). Imagining a gold Open Access future: Attitudes, behaviors, and funding scenarios among authors of academic scholarship. *College & Research Libraries*, 78(6), 824–843. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.78.6.824>
- Tenopir, C., Levine, K., Allard, S., Christian, L., Volentine, R., Boehm, R., Nichols, F., Nicholas, D., Jamali, H. R., Herman, E., & Watkinson, A. (2016). Trustworthiness and authority of scholarly information in a digital age: Results of an international questionnaire. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67(10), 2344–2361.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23598>

- The European University Institute (EU Exit) Regulations 2019*. (2019, February 19). GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/eu-withdrawal-act-2018-statutory-instruments/the-european-university-institute-eu-exit-regulation-2019>
- Tobin, C., Mavrommati, G., & Urban-Rich, J. (2020). Responding to social distancing in conducting stakeholder workshops in COVID-19 era. *Societies*, 10(4), 98. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc10040098>
- University of Sheffield. (2021). *University and legal requirements—Research Data Management*. The University of Sheffield. <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/library/rdm/requirements>
- van Raan, A. (2019). Measuring science: Basic principles and application of advanced bibliometrics. In W. Glänzel, H. F. Moed, U. Schmoch, & M. Thelwall (Eds.), *Springer handbook of science and technology indicators* (pp. 237–280). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-02511-3_10
- Vezzosi, M. (2009). Doctoral students' information behaviour: An exploratory study at the University of Parma (Italy). *New Library World*, 110(1/2), 65–80. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03074800910928595>
- Virkus, S. (2003). Information literacy in Europe: A literature review. *Information Research*, 8(4), 1–56.
- Virkus, S. (2012). Information literacy from the policy and strategy perspective. *Nordic Journal of Information Literacy in Higher Education*, 4(1), 16–37. <https://doi.org/10.15845/noril.v4i1.153>
- Virkus, S. (2013). Information Literacy in Europe: Ten years later. In S. Kurbanoglu, E. Grassian, D. Mizrachi, R. Catts, & S. Špiranec (Eds.), *Worldwide commonalities and challenges in Information Literacy research*

- and practice* (Vol. 397, pp. 250–257). Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-03919-0_32
- Vlog 32 *Information literacy for PhD students*. (2016, October 30).
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xv6Y66W-ezc&t=16s>
- Voegtle, E. M. (2014). *Higher education policy convergence and the Bologna process: A cross-national study*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- West, R. E., & Rich, P. J. (2012). Rigor, impact and prestige: A proposed framework for evaluating scholarly publications. *Innovative Higher Education*, 37(5), 359–371. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10755-012-9214-3>
- Wilkins, S., Hazzam, J., & Lean, J. (2021). Doctoral publishing as professional development for an academic career in higher education. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 19(1), 100459.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2021.100459>
- Wiorogórska, Z. (2014). Information Literacy and doctoral students in France and Poland. A comparative study. *Zagadnienia Informacji Naukowej - Studia Informacyjne*, 52(1(103)), 52–66. <https://doi.org/10.36702/zin.535>

8 Appendices

Appendix 1 – Web survey settings

- Requires sign-in OFF - Collect emails OFF - Restrict to users in University of Sheffield and its trusted organisations OFF (respondents were anonymous)
- Response receipts OFF (respondents did not get a receipt after the completion of the web survey)
- Edit after submit OFF
- See summary charts and text responses OFF
- Presentation: show progress bar ON
- Confirmation message: Your response has been recorded
- Make this a quiz (assign point values to questions and allow auto-marking) OFF

Appendix 2 – Information provided to the web survey participants

Trustworthiness in scholarly communication and information literacy competences in European doctoral students

Dr Federica Signoriello (fsignoriello1@sheffield.ac.uk), Webmaster and Information Librarian at the EUI Library, is completing a MA in Library and Information Services Management at the University of Sheffield, UK.

You are being invited to take part in the research project that will constitute Dr Signoriello's final dissertation. Before you decide whether or not to participate, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve.

If you decide to participate, you will answer a series of questions in a web survey, which takes between 10 and 15 minutes.

If you give your consent to be interviewed, you might be asked to participate in a brief semi-structured interview about the training you received from other universities in Europe before coming to the EUI.

Participation is voluntary; more information (scope, data management, more contacts) is provided in this information sheet:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1EKCaLZYqAjbScntC5stUWj5IXVbHZCq2WyZh-B2MhJQ/edit?usp=sharing>

By clicking NEXT and completing the survey, you are indicating that you:

- Have read and understood the project information sheet.
- Have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the project.
- Agree to complete a questionnaire.
- Understand that by choosing to participate as a volunteer in this research, this does not create a legally binding agreement nor is it intended to create an employment relationship with the University of Sheffield.
- Understand that your taking part is voluntary and that you can withdraw from the study at any time. You do not have to give any reasons for why you no longer want to take part and there will be no adverse consequences if you choose to withdraw.

- Understand that your personal details such as your name and email address (if you decide to disclose them) will not be revealed to other people than Dr Signoriello.
- Understand and agree that your words may be quoted in publications, reports, web pages, and other research outputs. You understand that you will not be named in these outputs.
- Understand and agree that other authorised researchers will have access to this data only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the information as requested in this form.
- Understand and agree that other authorised researchers may use my data in publications, reports, web pages, and other research outputs, only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the information as requested in this form.
- Give permission for the answers that you provide to be deposited in ORDA, the University of Sheffield's data repository so it can be used for future research and learning.
- Agree to assign the copyright you hold in any materials generated as part of this project to The University of Sheffield.

Appendix 3 – Additional information given to the web survey participants

Trustworthiness in scholarly communication and information literacy competences in European doctoral students

Dr Federica Signoriello, Webmaster and Information Librarian at the EUI Library, is completing a MA in Library and Information Services Management at the University of Sheffield, UK.

You are being invited to take part in the research project that will constitute Dr Signoriello's final dissertation. Before you decide whether or not to participate, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Thank you for reading this.

Purpose

- The first aim is that of investigating the topic of trustworthiness in doctoral students applied to the context of scholarly communication. As today's scholarly communication is mostly digital, its growth is constant and haphazard. Thus, recognising and trusting a journal, a platform or a publisher is not always a straight-forward process. Investigating the mindset and the opinions of doctoral students, i.e. researchers at the earliest stage of their career, could provide more insights and cues for future research.
- The second aim is that of investigating the correlation between the assessment of trustworthiness in doctoral students and their competences in information literacy. When students transition from a taught postgraduate course to a doctorate, not only do they carry with them the wealth of knowledge acquired through past courses, but they also transfer from programme to programme a set of skills. How much mastery of academic writing for publication and awareness of concepts like peer review, bibliometrics, open access and the differences between academic journals and publishers in the same field do they have? This second part of the research will also focus on the countries where doctoral researchers received their undergraduate and postgraduate education, taking into account the

mobility programmes promoted by European integration and the Bologna Process.

Why have I been chosen?

This invitation was sent to all doctoral candidates at the EUI because European doctoral students are the target population of this research.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep (and be asked to sign a consent form in case you give your consent to be interviewed) and you can still withdraw at any time without any negative consequences. You do not have to give a reason.

Please note that by choosing to participate in this research, this will not create a legally binding agreement, nor is it intended to create an employment relationship between you and the University of Sheffield.

What will happen to me if I take part? What do I have to do?

- First, you will answer a series of questions in a web survey.
- Afterwards, if you give your consent to be interviewed, you might be asked to participate in a brief semi-structured interview about the training you received from other universities in Europe before coming to the EUI.

Will my taking part in this project be kept confidential?

All the information collected about you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential and will only be accessible to Dr Signoriello. You will not be able to be identified in any reports or publications.

Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?

If you give your consent to be interviewed, the audio recordings of your activities made during this research will be used only for analysis. No other use will be made of them without your written permission, and no one other than Dr Signoriello will be allowed access to the original recordings.

What will happen to the data collected, and the results of the research project?

The data collected will be accessed only by Dr Signoriello. Her supervisor Prof. Peter Willett will have access to the anonymised data.

The results of the research will be published internally at the University of Sheffield and might be published in the form of a journal article.

The data provided will be stored in anonymised form for as long as needed (not further than 31 December 2021) in a on a folder provided by the University of Sheffield based on a Microsoft cluster service running on virtualised software hosted on-premise using dedicated hardware and on the central storage system of the University of Sheffield.

Due to the nature of this research it is very likely that other researchers may find the data collected to be useful in answering future research questions. We will ask for your explicit consent for your data to be shared in this way.

Who is the Data Controller?

The University of Sheffield will act as the Data Controller for this study. This means that the University of Sheffield is responsible for looking after your information and using it properly.

Who has ethically reviewed the project?

This project has been ethically approved via the University of Sheffield's Ethics Review Procedure, as administered by Information School.

What if something goes wrong and I wish to complain about the research?

Should you wish to raise a complaint, please contact Prof. Peter Willett (p.willett@sheffield.ac.uk)

Should you feel your complaint has not been handled to your satisfaction, please contact Prof. Gillet (v.gillet@sheffield.ac.uk).

If the complaint relates to how your personal data has been handled, information about how to raise a complaint can be found in the University of Sheffield's Privacy Notice: <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/govern/data-protection/privacy/general>

Appendix 4 – Web survey questions

Usage and reading behaviour

Q1. How important do you consider each of these activities when deciding what information to use/read in your own research area? Not important/
Somewhat important/ Important/ Very important/ Extremely important

1.1 Reading the abstract

1.2 Checking to see whether the data used in the research are credible

1.3 Checking whether the arguments and logic presented in the content are sound

1.4 Checking to see if it is peer reviewed

1.5 Checking whether the source is indexed by an authoritative indexing body
(e.g. LexisNexis, Web of Science, EconBiz, OpenEdition.org)

1.6 Taking into consideration colleagues' opinions of it

1.7 Taking account of where source was obtained from (e.g. publisher's website,
university library catalogue, search engine)

1.8 Checking the name of the publisher

1.9 Checking to see how many times it has been downloaded/ accessed

1.10 Checking whether author's country of affiliation is known for its research

Q2. To what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements?

Strongly disagree/Disagree/Neither agree nor disagree/Agree/Strongly agree

2.1 Peer reviewed journals are the most trustworthy information source

2.2 The journal's Impact Factor is important for deciding what to read

2.3 When pressed for time, the ease of availability of a source over-takes
considerations about its quality

2.4 If the information is not central to my research area, the ease of availability of a
source is more important than its quality

Disseminating and publishing

Q3. As an author, how important are the following attributes of an outlet when deciding where to disseminate/publish your research work? Not
important/Somewhat important/Important/Very important/Extremely important

3.1 It is peer reviewed

3.2 It is highly cited

3.3 It is published by a traditional scholarly publisher

3.4 It is published by a society in my field

3.5 It has both an online and a print version

3.6 It is Open Access

3.7 It is based in a country known for the quality of its research

Q4. To what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements concerning the quality and trustworthiness of places to publish/disseminate your research? Strongly disagree/ Disagree/ Neither agree nor disagree/ Agree/ Strongly agree

4.1 People who don't have tenure have to publish in good journals to build up a reputation

4.2 I publish in journals because a paper placed in a journal obtains a context, becomes part of a 'conversation'

4.3 I tend to publish first in a conference proceedings, which is a good way to test the veracity of my ideas

4.4 I tend to publish first in a conference proceedings, because it is a reliable way to reach my target audiences

4.5 Depositing a version of my published work in an institutional repository increases usage and thereby helps to build up my professional reputation among my peers

4.6 Depositing a version of my published work in an institutional repository increases citation and thereby helps to build up my professional reputation among my peers

4.7 I use social media (e.g. Twitter, blogs, social networks) to get out information about my research because it is a reliable way to reach my target audiences

4.8 My own website is central for ensuring the reliable dissemination of my work to my target audiences

4.9 I tend to blog about the findings of my research, which is a good way to test the veracity of my ideas

4.10 I tend to publish first in a subject repository (pre-publication database), such as ArXiv, PMC, RePEc, because it is a reliable way to reach wider audiences

Citing

Q5. How characteristic of your discipline are each of the citing practices listed below? Not characteristic/ Somewhat characteristic/ Characteristic/ Very characteristic/ Essential

5.1 Citing the most highly cited information sources

5.2 Citing the first information source published on a topic

5.3 Citing one's own work to improve one's citation ranking (e.g. H-Index)

5.4 Citing papers in the journal to which an article is submitted for publication to increase chances of acceptance

5.5 Citing papers mentioned by reviewers to increase chances of acceptance

5.6 Citing non-peer reviewed sources (e.g. personal correspondence, newspaper articles, blogs, tweets)

5.7 Citing a pre-print which has not yet been accepted by a journal

5.8 Citing sources disseminated with comments posted on a dedicated website (open peer review)

5.9 Citing, if possible, only sources published in developed countries

5.10 Citing the published version of record, but reading another version found on the open web

Q6. To what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements concerning the quality and trustworthiness of the sources you cite? Strongly disagree/ Disagree/ Neither agree nor disagree/ Agree/ Strongly agree

6.1 From a trust perspective I'm more easy-going in what I read than what I cite

6.2 I don't cite articles published in Open Access journals because they are of low quality

6.3 The journal Impact Factor is important for deciding what to cite

About you

What is your affiliation at the European University Institute? Department of Economics, Department of History and Civilisation, Department of Law, Department of Political and Social Sciences

What year are you? 1st year, 2n year, 3rd year, 4th+ year

What is your age? 20-25 years old, 25-30 years old, 30+ years old

Where did you study before starting this PhD programme at the European University Institute (the country where you attended a Master's or Bachelor programme)? Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom, other

Further information

If you give your consent to be interviewed by Dr Signoriello, please write your email address below, otherwise leave blank

Is there any comment you would like to make before ending this survey?

Appendix 5 – Interview questions

- What was your academic route to PhD?
- About your university education before your PhD:
 - What kind of master's degree did you attain before your PhD and where?
 - Did you learn how to find material to read for assignments during your master's degree? How?
 - Did you learn how to cite during your master's degree? How?
 - Did you acquire any knowledge about how and where to publish, Open Access, and impact during your master's degree?
 - Did your previous university/ies organise courses about finding material to read, citing, publishing?
 - If yes, what was the nature of these courses? Were they elective or compulsory? Who taught them?
 - If no, how did you learn about these topics? Did you teach yourself or did anyone else teach you?
- About your PhD:
 - What did you learn about these topics during your PhD and how?

Appendix 6 – Grounded theory coding

Codes	Categories	Sub-categories
PhD: the relationship with supervisor is key to learning about scholarly communication	causes	supervisor's approach to information literacy
Research-related job	causes	research related job
Research-related job not teaching scholarly communication	causes	research related job
Research-related job teaching scholarly communication	causes	research related job
University expectation of self-teaching	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University focusing on peer-review	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University lenient towards citing	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University not providing citation courses	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University not providing courses on how to publish	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University not providing courses on searching bibliographies	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University organising a course on how to publish	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University organising courses on academic writing	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University organising no training whatsoever	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University pressing against plagiarism	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University providing all kind of courses	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University providing citing instructions	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University providing courses on bibliographical databases	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University providing courses on citing	causes	university's approach to information literacy
University providing handouts	causes	university's approach to information literacy
Not following a course on how to publish	causes	student's attitude
Not following a course on using databases	causes	student's attitude
Not following courses because of personal circumstances	causes	student's attitude

Reading lists	causes	supervisor's approach to information literacy
Supervisor providing general help	causes	supervisor's approach to information literacy
Supervisor suggesting bibliography	causes	supervisor's approach to information literacy
PhD improvements: commitment to Open Access	consequences	commitment to OA
PhD improvements: publishing in a network	consequences	publishing
Desire to be trained on how to publish	consequences	self-awareness of one's skills
Publishing via conference proceedings	consequences	publishing
Regret not to have learnt crucial tools	consequences	self-awareness of one's skills
Not publishing	consequences	not publishing
Supervisor telling their own experience with publishing	context	supervisor's attitude to publishing and scholarly communication
Belarusian journal classification	context	national publishing culture
Italian journal classification	context	national publishing culture
Different approaches about citing in the same university	context	university's attitude to publishing and scholarly communication
No pressure on publishing in prestigious journals	context	university's attitude to publishing and scholarly communication
University pushing towards PhD	context	university's attitude to publishing and scholarly communication
University's lack of library resources	context	university's availability of resources
Supervisor suggesting where to publish	context	supervisor's attitude to publishing and scholarly communication
PhD improvements: focusing on journal prestige	phenomena	knowledge of how to publish
PhD improvements: how the publication industry works	phenomena	knowledge of scholarly communication
PhD improvements: how to find bibliography	phenomena	knowledge of how to publish
PhD improvements: how to publish (informal learning)	phenomena	knowledge of how to publish
PhD improvements: peer review	phenomena	knowledge of how to publish
PhD improvements: understanding scholarly communication	phenomena	knowledge of scholarly communication
PhD improvements: why publishing is good practice	phenomena	knowledge of scholarly communication
PhD not improving knowledge on scholarly communication	phenomena	knowledge of scholarly communication
Bibliometrics are spreading in Eastern Europe	phenomena	knowledge of scholarly communication

Bibliometrics are useful in law	phenomena	knowledge of scholarly communication
Bibliometrics not useful in law	phenomena	knowledge of scholarly communication
Citing the paper copy is better	phenomena	knowledge of how to publish
Getting published is tiresome	phenomena	difficulties in publishing
No knowledge of bibliometrics	phenomena	knowledge about scholarly communication
Publishing is tiresome	phenomena	difficulties in publishing
Citing favours	phenomena	knowledge of how to publish
Introduction to academia	phenomena	knowledge of scholarly communication
Open Access in Eastern Europe	phenomena	knowledge of scholarly communication
Publishing difficult in Economics	phenomena	difficulties in publishing
Citation chain	strategies	self-teaching
Citation chain with top journals	strategies	self-teaching
Learning how to publish from peers	strategies	learning from peers
Learning how to search from peers	strategies	learning from peers
Learning scholarly communication from peers	strategies	learning from peers
Publishing for journals catering early career scholars	strategies	publishing
Publishing via networking	strategies	networking
Self-teaching citing	strategies	self-teaching
Self-teaching searching techniques	strategies	self-teaching
PhD improvements: self-teaching publishing through trial and error	strategies	self-teaching

Appendix 7 – Research Ethics application form

Application 037198

Section A: Applicant details

Date application started:

Sun 8 November 2020 at 18:31

First name:

Federica

Last name:

Signoriello

Email:

fsignoriello1@sheffield.ac.uk

Programme name:

MA in Library and Information Services Management

Module name:

Dissertation

Last updated:

21/12/2020

Department:

Information School

Applying as:

Undergraduate / Postgraduate taught

Research project title:

Trustworthiness in scholarly communication and information literacy competences in European doctoral students

Has your research project undergone academic review, in accordance with the appropriate process?

Yes

Similar applications:

- not entered -

Section B: Basic information

Supervisor

Name

Email

Peter Willett

p.willett@sheffield.ac.uk

Proposed project duration

Start date (of data collection):

Thu 10 December 2020

Anticipated end date (of project)

Wed 31 March 2021

3: Project code (where applicable)

Project externally funded?

- not entered -

Project code
- *not entered* -

Suitability

Takes place outside UK?

Yes

Involves NHS?

No

Health and/or social care human-interventional study?

No

ESRC funded?

No

Likely to lead to publication in a peer-reviewed journal?

No

Led by another UK institution?

No

Involves human tissue?

No

Clinical trial or a medical device study?

No

Involves social care services provided by a local authority?

No

Is social care research requiring review via the University Research Ethics Procedure

No

Involves adults who lack the capacity to consent?

No

Involves research on groups that are on the Home Office list of 'Proscribed terrorist groups or organisations'?

No

Indicators of risk

Involves potentially vulnerable participants?

No

Involves potentially highly sensitive topics?

No

Section C: Summary of research

1. Aims & Objectives

1) Investigate the topic of trustworthiness in doctoral students applied to the context of scholarly communications. Given the haphazard growth of scholarly communications in today's digital world, recognising and trusting a journal, a platform or a publisher is not always a straight-forward process. By investigating the mindset and the opinions of doctoral students, i.e. researchers at the earliest stage of their career, can provide revealing insights and cues for future research.

2) Investigate the correlation between the assessment of trustworthiness in doctoral students and their competences in information literacy.

When students transition from a taught postgraduate course to a doctorate, not only do they carry with them the wealth of knowledge acquired through past courses, but they also transfer a set of skills from programme to programme. Initially, these should allow them to perform efficiently information seeking, reading and citing. Their competence in information literacy, in fact, hardly encompasses the complex network of platforms and tools that scholars employ to share their work, that is, knowledge of scholarly communications. Postgraduate students, therefore, may reach the doctoral programmes with none or little mastery of academic writing for publication and awareness of concepts like peer

review, bibliometrics, open access and the differences between academic journals and publishers in the same field. This, however, might not be true in the same extent for all doctoral candidates in Europe, as the approach to information literacy varies significantly across European countries.

3) Compare findings with those of [Nicholas, D., Jamali, H. R., Watkinson, A., Herman, E., Tenopir, C., Volentine, R., Allard, S., & Levine, K. (2015). Do younger researchers assess trustworthiness differently when deciding what to read and cite and where to publish? *International Journal of Knowledge Content Development & Technology*, 5(2), 45–63. <https://doi.org/10.5865/IJKCT.2015.5.2.045>] to ascertain (i) the differences between those who in that study were defined

as “younger researchers” and current doctoral students (ii) whether the different geographical focus plays any role.

4) Examine the existing literature about these topics: trustworthiness in reading, citing and publishing; the competences in information literacy of doctoral students; the issue of publishing during the doctoral programme.

5) Make recommendations for future research.

2. Methodology

The study for this dissertation will be carried out with mixed methods research, and it will therefore focus on collecting, analysing, and mixing both quantitative and qualitative data.

More specifically, it will adopt an explanatory sequential mixed methods design, which involves a two-phase data collection:

a) Quantitative data collection will entail replicating the study by [Nicholas, D., Jamali, H. R., Watkinson, A., Herman, E., Tenopir, C., Volentine, R., Allard, S., & Levine, K. (2015). Do younger researchers assess trustworthiness differently when deciding what to read and cite and where to publish? *International Journal of Knowledge Content Development & Technology*, 5(2), 45–63. <https://doi.org/10.5865/IJKCT.2015.5.2.045>] among European doctoral students of Humanities and Social Sciences. This will be implemented via a web-based survey delivered through Google Forms. This questionnaire relies on Likert scales ranking the importance or agreement with 24 given statements.

b) Qualitative follow-up interviews. These will be carried out with those respondents of phase (a) who may represent categories created on the basis of significant results of phase (a).

Data analysis will be fourfold:

(i) Analysis of quantitative data.

(ii) Comparing results with those from the research conducted by Nicholas to ascertain possible alignments.

(iii) Analysis of qualitative data.

(iv) Integration.

3. Personal Safety

Have you completed your departmental risk assessment procedures, if appropriate?

Not applicable

Raises personal safety issues?

No

There are no issues of personal safety for me as I will not work outside normal hours, nor with potentially threatening people and I will not conduct activities in a potentially dangerous environment.

Section D: About the participants

1. Potential Participants

The research will be carried out at the European University Institute (EUI), an international research institute founded in 1976 and located in Florence, Italy. To this day, 24 member states of the European Union have joined the EUI and finance the research of about 600 European doctoral students in four departments: Economics, Law, History and Civilisation, and Political and Social Sciences. The sampling of participants, therefore, will not be actively sought, but the regulation of the EUI (Convention setting up a European University Institute: As revised by the 1992 Amending Convention, n.d.) guarantees the status of doctoral student and a variety of European nationalities among partakers.

2. Recruiting Potential Participants

The web-survey for phase (a) of data collection will be sent via email to all active doctoral researchers through the departmental email distribution lists.

The interviewees for phase (b) of the qualitative follow up interviews will be contacted among those who gave their consent to being contacted by writing their email address.

2.1. Advertising methods

Will the study be advertised using the volunteer lists for staff or students maintained by CICS? No

- not entered -

3. Consent

Will informed consent be obtained from the participants? (i.e. the proposed process) Yes

In the web-survey of phase (a) of data collection, implied consent will be given through the completion and return of a questionnaire.

As for phase (b) of the qualitative follow up interviews, interviewees will sign a separate consent form.

4. Payment

Will financial/in kind payments be offered to participants? No

5. Potential Harm to Participants

What is the potential for physical and/or psychological harm/distress to the participants?

The content and line of questioning may be sensitive, may raise confidential personal issues, and may intrude, or be perceived to intrude, upon a participant's comfort and privacy.

How will this be managed to ensure appropriate protection and well-being of the participants?

Before participating, people should be informed of how to contact the researcher, who will be able to escalate their concern, within a reasonable time period, if, following participation, they experience stress, harm or have any other concerns about the research.

Section E: About the data

1. Data Processing

Will you be processing (i.e. collecting, recording, storing, or otherwise using) personal data as part of this project? (Personal data is any information relating to an identified or identifiable living person).

No

Please outline how your data will be managed and stored securely, in line with good practice and relevant funder requirements

Survey results, audio recordings of the interviews and transcriptions of the interviews will be stored on my Sheffield UniDrive.

Section F: Supporting documentation

Information & Consent

Participant information sheets relevant to project?

Yes

[Document 1085812 \(Version 1\)](#)

[All versions](#)

Consent forms relevant to project?

Yes

[Document 1085813 \(Version 1\)](#)

[All versions](#)

Additional Documentation

External Documentation

- not entered -

Section G: Declaration

Signed by:
Federica Signoriello
Date signed:
Fri 18 December 2020 at 19:23

Official notes

- not entered -

Appendix 8 – Ethics certificate of approval

Downloaded: 22/12/2020
Approved: 21/12/2020

Federica Signoriello
Registration number: 180140987
Information School
Programme: MA in Library and Information Services Management

Dear Federica

PROJECT TITLE: Trustworthiness in scholarly communication and information literacy competences in European doctoral students

APPLICATION: Reference Number 037198

On behalf of the University ethics reviewers who reviewed your project, I am pleased to inform you that on 21/12/2020 the above-named project was **approved** on ethics grounds, on the basis that you will adhere to the following documentation that you submitted for ethics review:

- University research ethics application form 037198 (form submission date: 18/12/2020); (expected project end date: 31/03/2021).
- Participant information sheet 1085812 version 1 (18/12/2020).
- Participant consent form 1085813 version 1 (18/12/2020).

If during the course of the project you need to [deviate significantly from the above-approved documentation](#) please inform me since written approval will be required.

Your responsibilities in delivering this research project are set out at the end of this letter.

Yours sincerely

Paul Reilly
Ethics Administrator
Information School

Please note the following responsibilities of the researcher in delivering the research project:

- The project must abide by the University's Research Ethics Policy: <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/rs/ethicsandintegrity/ethicspolicy/approval-procedure>
- The project must abide by the University's Good Research & Innovation Practices Policy: https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/polopoly_fs/1.671066!/file/GRIPPpolicy.pdf
- The researcher must inform their supervisor (in the case of a student) or Ethics Administrator (in the case of a member of staff) of any significant changes to the project or the approved documentation.
- The researcher must comply with the requirements of the law and relevant guidelines relating to security and confidentiality of personal data.
- The researcher is responsible for effectively managing the data collected both during and after the end of the project in line with best practice, and any relevant legislative, regulatory or contractual requirements.

Appendix 9 – Data Management Plan

Data Management Plan

a. Data definition

- Data collected during the project, not available elsewhere, is A) quantitative data about trustworthiness in European doctoral students applied to the context of scholarly communication; quantitative data about trustworthiness of “younger researchers” are provided by the study of Nicholas et al. (2015) and used as a comparator B) Qualitative data about the acquisition of information literacy skills of European doctoral students before starting their PhD programme.
- Data collection: A) through the use of a web survey and in the form of results from Nicholas et al. (2015) B) through semi-structured interviews.
- Format: A) Data from the web survey carried out with the web-based survey administration software Google Forms will be exported in .csv and .xls files. B) Data collected from interviews will be generated in audio format in .mp4 and transcribed in .docx documents.

b. Data storage

- Digital and physical storage: Data will be safely stored in two locations: the researcher’s folder provided by the University of Sheffield’s IT Service (UniDrive), which is password protected, and the researcher’s external hard drive.
- File naming: A folder structure and a file naming convention will be devised at the start of the project. Elements within the file names, consistently ordered, will be informative and standardised in terms of vocabulary, punctuation and numerical format.
- Backup of data: Backup of data is ensured by its double location and by the University of Sheffield data storage system.
- Frequency of backup: Data will be backed up whenever a new file will be generated.

c. Archiving data

- Long-term data storage: Data held on the University of Sheffield's storage space will be deleted after the assessment of the dissertation. Data will be retained in case of publication of the dissertation in the form of a journal article. For this purpose, data on the researcher's external drive will be retained and backed up in another password-protected cloud service to be determined after the assessment of the dissertation.

Appendix 10 – Risk assessment

Activity being assessed:	Trustworthiness in scholarly communication and information literacy competences in European doctoral students	Reference no:	180140987 (student number)
Location:	Working from home	Risk Assessment date:	01/10/2020
		Research activity period:	01/10/2020 – 31/07/2021

Significant Hazards What could cause harm?	What harm might occur, and to whom? Remember to consider all affected groups	Existing control measures	Risk Rating (with current controls)			Additional control measures What can we do / use / put in place to further reduce the risks to an acceptable level?	Residual Risk			Action no. (continues over page)
			L	S	RR		L	S	RR	
Display screen equipment use	Posture problems, eyesight problems from pveruse. Headaches and sore eyes in poor lighting conditions.	Set up a clear workstation with laptop on desk in a suitably well-lit environment. Take regular breaks away from the screen.	4	2	8	DSE training to refresh on suitable workstations and use of screens	2	2	4	

Action number	Action required	Who is responsible?	By when?	Date completed
1	Take display screen equipment training	me	31/12/2020	31/12/2020

L = likelihood, S = severity, RR = risk rating

Likelihood	Guide Description
5	Very likely/imminent – certain to happen
4	Probable – a strong possibility of it happening
3	Possible – it may have happened before
2	Unlikely - could happen but unusual
1	Rare – highly unlikely to occur

Severity	Guide Description
5	Catastrophic - fatality, catastrophic damage
4	Major – significant injury or property damage, hospitalisation
3	Moderate - injury requiring further treatment, lost time
2	Minor - first aid injury, no lost time
1	Very minor – insignificant injury

Likelihood (L)	Severity (S)					Risk Rating (RR)	Action
	1	2	3	4	5		
5	5	10	15	20	25	High Risk	Stop the task/activity until controls can be put into place to reduce the risk to an acceptable level
4	4	8	12	16	20	Medium Risk	Determine if further safety precautions are required to reduce risk to as low as is reasonably practicable
3	3	6	9	12	15		
2	2	4	6	8	10		
1	1	2	3	4	5	Low Risk	No further action, keep under review